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Electron transfer from singlet fission dimers: possibilities and limitations[†]

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Photocatalytic production of H₂ or hydrocarbons requires multiple electrons, and therefore the absorption of multiple photons and accumulation of photoexcited charges. Alternatively, multiexciton generation (MEG) could loosen this requirement. Despite intense studies of the MEG process singlet fission (SF) for solar cells, its use in photocatalysis has only recently been demonstrated. Herein, we present a detailed investigation of electron transfer (ET) from two tetracene based SF dimers, on time scales spanning the initial singlet excited state–triplet pair (TT) equilibrium and the longer-lived free triplet states. We find that the TT state behaves similarly to the singlet and thus can be used to increase the lifetime of singlet reactivity. We also show that in these covalently linked SF dimers, where TT recombines to form one free triplet, achieving more than 100% ET is challenging. Together with these findings and the input from theoretical calculations, we discuss the possibilities and limitations of ET from these dimers. By highlighting strategies to mitigate detrimental TT recombination pathways, these insights provide design principles for next-generation SF chromophores tailored for solar energy conversion and photoredox catalysis.

Introduction

In 1912, Professor Giacomo Ciamician proposed that using sunlight to drive chemical reactions would be the best way to reduce humankind's reliance on fossil fuels.¹ Over a century later, efforts towards this goal are as important as ever to mitigate the worst effects of climate change. A cornerstone in solar-to-fuel production is photocatalysis, which in turn often relies on photoinduced charge transfer (CT) events. However, for photocatalytic production of H₂ or hydrocarbons, the chemical reactions require multiple electrons to proceed. Since photochemical processes, such as photoinduced CT, usually adhere to the Stark-Einstein photo equivalence law, i.e. for each photon only one primary photochemical event will occur² multiple photons must be absorbed and the photoexcited

charges (electrons and/or holes) accumulated to produce the final fuel. This challenge has similarities to thermalisation losses in solar cells, where regardless of the energy of the absorbed photon, only one electron-hole pair can be generated. One way of overcoming thermalisation losses in solar cells, which has gathered intense research interest, is multiexciton generation (MEG). MEG, where one photon results in the formation of multiple excited states, has been observed in both inorganic and organic materials.^{3–8} In organic materials MEG typically proceeds through singlet fission (SF), where an initially photoexcited singlet state is split into two triplet-excited states.^{8–10} The commonly accepted mechanism of SF is described as:¹⁰

here S_0 , S_1 , and T_1 , are the ground state singlet, first excited singlet and first excited triplet state, respectively. Upon photoexcitation of one chromophore, it can couple with a neighbouring molecule in the ground state to form a triplet pair state with overall singlet spin (1TT). This state can eventually lose electronic coupling to form a spin-correlated triplet pair ${}^1[T\dots T]$, which upon loss of spin-coherence generates two triplet excited states ($T_1 + T_1$).¹⁰ Since these intermediate states are overall singlet in character, SF is spin-allowed and therefore can occur on ultrafast timescales, with triplet yields close to 200%.^{9–12} Hence, it is fundamentally different from intersystem crossing (ISC), which is spin-forbidden and proceeds with a maximum triplet yield of 100%. The weakly coupled triplet pair state can, however, interconvert between

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different spin-states (singlet, $S = 0$, triplet $S = 1$, and quintet $S = 2$). Since optical spectroscopy cannot directly distinguish between weakly and strongly bound triplet pair states, in the remaining text, we will refer to both types as the TT state.

Chromophores must meet certain criteria for the SF process to proceed. The primary energetic requirement is that the singlet excited state energy should exceed the combined energy of the two triplet excited states, according to the relation $E_{S_1} \geq 2E_{T_1}$. Another energetic requirement is that the energy level of higher lying triplet excited states should exceed $2 \times E_{T_1}$, that is, $E_{T_n(n>1)} \geq 2E_{T_1}$ so as to avoid their formation by triplet-triplet annihilation (TTA).⁹ Together with these energetic considerations, the interacting chromophores must possess sufficient coupling to enable rapid and efficient singlet-to-triplet pair conversion, allowing it to compete effectively with other deactivation pathways such as fluorescence. Therefore, SF occurs most efficiently in solid state films, crystals, and in molecular dimers or oligomers in solution. However, the coupling should not be too large as then, the TT remains bound and deactivation will mostly occur by TTA. Hence a balanced interchromophoric coupling is desired to facilitate the dissociation of the TT to free triplet states.^{11–14} Another key factor for the dissociation of the TT is the possibility of triplet hopping, which enhances the entropic gain of the process. The feasibility for spatial separation of triplet excitons increases the efficiency of SF in solid-state systems.^{13,15}

Even though SF has been studied intensely over the last decade for its use in solar cells, its use in photocatalysis has only recently been proposed and demonstrated in SF dimers.^{16,17} Covalently linked dimers offer strict control of distance and electronic coupling between two chromophores compared to crystal films and nanoparticles.^{18–20} Yet, the separation of the triplet pair into free triplets can be especially problematic in dimers. Conformational fluctuations are considered to drive the separation to free triplets from the intermediate TT state in some cases,^{21,22} however, competing pathways for the dissociation of the triplet pair have been identified:^{23–25}

$^1TT \rightarrow S_0S_0$ Singlet channel (loss of $\leq 100\%$ of triplets)

$^3TT \rightarrow T_1S_0$ Triplet channel (loss of $\leq 50\%$ of triplets)

$^1TT \rightarrow T_1S_0$ Intersystem crossing (loss of $\leq 50\%$ of triplets)

Dimers, which allow for SF in solution, would be particularly relevant for photocatalysis. Hence, understanding how to control and use the triplet pair and free triplets for ET reactions is necessary to address fundamental questions such as *what enables efficient multi-ET from SF dimers?* Liu *et al.* highlighted that trimers and tetramers are more efficient than dimers for sequential two ET due to the increased separation between the formed charges.²⁶ On the other hand, Nakamura *et al.* demonstrated photoinduced ET yields of 170–180% for a biphenyl-linked tetracene dimer with chloranil as the electron

Figure 1: Structures of molecules (a) and steady state absorption of Tc based molecules (b) used in this study.

acceptor.²⁷ Both of these examples established ET from the free triplets ($T_1 + T_1$), much less is known of what dictates ET from the triplet pair states and if it is possible to extract two electrons (holes) already from these states. In a pentacene-ironoxide cluster no ET was observed from the 1TT state, whereas it was observed for the free triplets, suggesting that the triplet pair and free triplets have distinct chemical properties.²⁸ Interestingly, in 2018 Kim *et al.* suggested that concerted two ET from 1TT was possible from tetracyanomethylene quinoidal bithiophene derivatives.²⁹ It has also been observed that charge separation from 1TT in solar cell blends is possible.³⁰ Although

the energy of the TT state is close to that of the singlet state, achieving photochemistry from this state would be valuable as the TT state can live longer as its recombination can be spin forbidden.³¹

One of the most studied acenes in SF, tetracene (Tc), is especially attractive for exploring ET processes relevant to photocatalysis. Fast SF in Tc-based chromophores yields triplet quantum yields close to 200%. Tetracene is also one of the few SF materials with a relatively high triplet energy of ~1.3 eV, making it possible to study ET to a wider variety of electron acceptors.³²

In this study, we clearly illustrate the difference in quenching between the TT/S₁ equilibrium state and the free triplet state in two TIPS-Tc dimers, a newly synthesised **Tcdimer** and a previously reported²⁷ **Tc-BP-Tc**, Figure 1. This was done by using a range of electron and hole acceptors with varying redox potentials, enabling thermodynamically favourable CT quenching from either the TT or triplet states. Building on these findings, we discuss the possibilities and limitations of using such covalently linked SF systems for ET applications in photocatalysis and solar cells.

Results and discussion

Synthesis and design of the SF materials

Two dimers were synthesized for our study. As a reference **Tc-BP-Tc** was synthesized according to published procedures.²⁷ To extend the scope of SF dimers we also designed a new **Tcdimer**. To enhance solubility, a phenyl linker with alkoxyhexyl side-groups was used. The linker **L-3**, composed of a phenyl unit modified with alkoxyhexyl groups was synthesized by nucleophilic substitution of phenolic groups (ESI Section 2.1). After modification through standard Sonogashira coupling followed by deprotection with TBAF, linker **L-3** was obtained with two acetylene functional groups, with an overall yield of 16% for the 3 steps (ESI Section 2.1).

Scheme 1: Synthetic routes for **Tcdimer** and **Tcmonomer**.

Subsequent coupling with two TIPS-Tc units through Sonogashira coupling conditions, afforded **Tcdimer** with 56% yield (Scheme 1). As a monomeric reference, **Tcmonomer** was synthesized in a similar manner using commercially available phenyl acetylene (Ph-ac) as the coupling partner (Scheme 1).

Photophysical and electrochemical characterisation of **Tcdimer**

The steady state absorption spectrum of **Tcdimer** shows the characteristic vibronic peaks of tetracene between 450-550 nm (Figure 1). These are slightly red shifted (~5 nm) with respect to **Tcmonomer**. The strong absorption bands in the range 380-420 nm of the **Tcdimer** spectrum are absent in both the TIPS-Tc and the isolated linker (**L-3**) (Figure S59), suggesting that the transitions responsible for these features arise from cooperative contributions of both components. Computational analysis of the electronic excitations in **Tcdimer**, in comparison with TIPS-Tc and the linker (Figures S60-S62), reveals the presence of absorption bands that are unique to **Tcdimer**. These transitions are characterized by electronic excitations with partial CT character involving both TIPS-Tc moieties and the linker.

Whereas the fluorescence quantum yield of TIPS-Tc is around 80%,³³ it drops to 23% in the case of **Tcmonomer**. This could be due to energy losses around the rotation of the phenylacetylene, although an increased rate of ISC was also observed for the **Tcmonomer**, revealed by the fast decay of the

Figure 2: (a) fsTA spectra of **Tcdimer** (60 μM) in THF excited at 500 nm. (b) nsTA spectra of **Tcdimer** in THF (10 μM) excited at 545 nm. (c) The corresponding time profile of **Tcdimer** at 525 nm. (d) Evolution associated spectra (EAS) of the fs-TA spectra shown in (a). (e) Cyclic voltammogram of the reduction wave of **Tcdimer** (133 μM) in DCM in 0.1 M TBAPF6 with 100 mvs $^{-1}$ scan rate (upper) and cyclic voltammogram of the reduction wave of **Tcmonomer** (133 μM) in DCM in 0.1 M TBAPF6 with 100 mvs $^{-1}$ scan rate (lower) (f) Transient EPR measurements on **Tcdimer** and **Tcmonomer**, recorded at 80 K, the spectra are integrated over 0.4–0.6 μs after photoexcitation. The experimental spectra are scaled to the maximum absolute intensity. The data for the **Tcmonomer** are presented alongside a numerical simulation, see ESI for simulation details.

singlet state to form the triplet state within 6 ns (Figure S28 and Figure S30). Notably, the relative orientation of the two TIPS-Tc units in **Tcdimer** can give rise to two conformers, denoted syn and anti. Electronic structure calculations indicate that both are nearly isoenergetic (Figure S63). Furthermore, the small computed energy barrier for their interconversion through rotation around the acetylene units of the linker ($DE \approx 1$ kcal/mol) suggests rapid dynamic interconversion. Furthermore, photophysical properties of the syn and anti-conformers are expected to be indistinguishable based on computed electronic excitation energies (Figure S63). Nonetheless, the quantum yield of **Tcdimer** (16%) is lower than **Tcmonomer**. Time-resolved fluorescence (TCSPC) reveals monoexponential decays for **TIPS-Tc** and **Tcmonomer**, but a triexponential decay for **Tcdimer** (Figure S20 and S21). The second and third decay components, much longer than the **Tcmonomer** lifetime, suggests that at least one additional long-lived state beyond the singlet would be involved. The steady state absorption, fluorescence and time-resolved fluorescence of **Tcdimer** in different solvents are given in (Figure S20). The steady-state absorption spectra exhibit only minor solvent-dependent variations, with shifts of approximately 2 nm between THF and toluene, and about 4 nm between toluene and benzonitrile (PhCN). In contrast, the fluorescence spectrum in PhCN shows a modest red shift of roughly 10 nm relative to the other two solvents. Additionally, the second component of the fluorescence lifetime is noticeably shorter in PhCN, indicating faster nonradiative decay of the long-lived state in the more polar solvent environment.

Transient Absorption and EPR of Tcdimer. To further probe the excited state dynamics of **Tcdimer** and to understand the long-lived state(s) involved, we now turn to transient absorption both on the femtosecond (fsTA) and nanosecond (nsTA) timescales. The fsTA spectra of **Tcdimer** in THF (Figure 2a), upon exciting at 500 nm, show ESA between 400–750 nm, with overlapping ground state bleaching (GSB) signals at 425 nm, 500 nm and 545 nm, and stimulated emission (SE) at 600 nm. The red part of the spectra (550–630 nm) rises rapidly within 100 ps along with a corresponding decrease in the blue part (400–450 nm). A persistent GSB signal at 545 nm, together with two isosbestic points at 370 and 640 nm can be seen during the spectral evolution, suggesting a quantitative conversion between two species. A satisfactory fit is obtained using global analysis with a three-state consecutive model. The evolution-associated spectra thus acquired are provided in (Figure 2d) and (Figure S29). We assign the spectral evolution to the S_1 state conversion to the TT state via a CT intermediate ($S_1S_0^{CT}$), based on the similarities to a previously reported Tc dimer.³⁴ The CT intermediate is rationalised by us and others, by the increased rate of formation in polar PhCN.³⁴ This mechanism is also supported by the CT component in the initially excited S_1 state, which has been shown to facilitate CT coupling with the triplet pair and rapid SF.^{35,36} We do not attribute the observed kinetics to different conformers, as our calculations of the major conformers (Section S14.2) show that their relevant electronic states are nearly isoenergetic. Despite the equilibrium between the TT and singlet states suggested by the repopulation observed in the PL data, we employ a three-state consecutive model for the fsTA analysis because the repopulation

occurs on timescales significantly longer than those captured in the fsTA measurements.

Nevertheless, the data suggest that the S_1 state converts to the TT state within 200 ps. In contrast, the fsTA spectra of **Tcmonomer** (Figure S28) show a much slower decay of the singlet (~6 ns)

Further evidence for SF in **Tcdimer** can be obtained from transient electron paramagnetic resonance spectroscopy (tr-EPR). This technique can detect distinct triplet sublevel populations and thereby distinguish between ISC and SF-born triplets. Particularly, it can detect the quintet state ($S=2$), which is unique to SF. The tr-EPR spectrum of **Tcmonomer** and **Tcdimer** are compared in Figure 2f. The **Tcmonomer** shows a broad triplet state spectrum with an eeeaa polarisation pattern; the spectral width/splittings are determined by the zero-field (ZF) interaction matrix and the electron-spin polarisation arises from the transformation of the spin states developed during the intersystem crossing process to the high-field eigenstates, which is mediated by spin-orbit coupling interactions and is selective to the ZF spin sublevels.³⁷ The tr-EPR spectrum of **Tcdimer** consists of outer and inner features, both of which are present at the earliest timescales accessible by the experiment. The inner features are assigned to a 5TT state, the field positions of the intense emissive and absorptive peaks are consistent with the $|2, \pm 1\rangle \leftrightarrow |2, 0\rangle$ transitions for the xy orientations, assuming collinear ZF-interaction matrices of the two triplets in the TT state. The outer features are assigned to free triplet states, the resemblance of the electron-spin polarisation pattern across this region to the Tcmonomer spectrum, suggests the presence of ISC born triplets. These assignments are supported by pulse transient nutation experiments that clearly indicate the presence of both triplet and quintet states, see ESI (Figure S58). After the first ten microseconds following photoexcitation, the trEPR signal has largely decayed and, during this time, the overall spin-polarisation patterns for the triplet and quintet contributions are preserved. The exact mechanism responsible for the genesis of the spin polarisation observed in the quintet state is an open question. It was recently suggested that 1TT can undergo ISC to form T_1 , which could be a possibility in the current case.²⁵ Simulations considering linear combinations of triplet states (formed either via ISC or from a high-field precursor) and quintet/triplet-pair states (with either high-field eigenstate or singlet-character population schemes and considering different coupling strengths) have, so far, been unable to adequately and uniquely model the entire spectrum for **Tcdimer**.

In the nsTA spectra of Tcdimer in THF (Figure 2b), we see features similar to the last spectra seen in fsTA. Also, these resemble the spectra of the sensitized triplet. Hence these features arise from a triplet-like species. The decay monitored at 525 nm (Figure 2c) is clearly biphasic. An initial fast component, with a decay constant of 107 ns, is followed by a plateau at approximately 50% of the initial intensity. This intermediate state then decays more slowly, with a time constant of 240 μ s. The longer decay is assigned to the decay of one free triplet. Support for this interpretation is provided by

the decay of the triplet plateau being similar to the lifetime of an isolated triplet, as observed for the triplet decay of **Tcmonomer** (Figure S33). In the case of a decoupled $T_1 + T_1$ state, the decay would proceed with a distinct, shorter lifetime due to TTA.³⁸ Since the conformational fluctuations that would give rise to the decoupled triplet states are reversible, geminate TTA is expected to enhance the decay of the triplet features compared to the monomer without TTA, which is not observed in this case.

We also performed low temperature nsTA at 100 K in methyl-THF (MeTHF) to allow direct comparison with the EPR data, Figure S54. Interestingly, the fast decay of the nsTA kinetics at 525 nm, occurs on the same time scale as the quintet triplet pair features from tr-EPR decay. Hence, we assign the first shorter decay seen in nsTA kinetics (Figure 2c and S54) to that of the TT state. However, since the decay in tr-EPR arises not only from decay to the ground state, but also through loss of spin-polarization, we cannot rule out that the nsTA signal also includes other EPR-silent states.

To summarize, SF to form the TT state occurs over 200 ps. This is followed by triplet pair (TT) decay into only one free triplet over 100 ns. The remaining free triplet then decays monoexponentially over 240 μ s. Similar TT decay into one free triplet has been reported for many moderately and strongly coupled dimers, with the proposed mechanism involving spin evolution of the $^{2S+1}[T...T]$ state to 3TT , followed by internal conversion to T_1 .³⁸⁻⁴² Another possible pathway is 1TT decay to T_1 via ISC, which was recently demonstrated by Ali et al.²⁵ in anthradithiophene films. The kinetics in THF thus suggest a triplet yield less than 100% and we quantify the triplet yield using three independent methods (ESI Section 8). First, from the fsTA spectra, the S_1 and TT basis spectra are constructed and then normalised to the GSB they share. The resulting quantitative population dynamics suggest 100% formation of the TT from the S_1 state (200% triplets). Based on the nsTA spectra, and assuming that the GSB contributions of the TT and T_1 GSB scale with the number of monomers they occupy (*i.e.*, 2:1), we quantify the population dynamics (see ESI section 8.2.1 for details). The analysis suggests close to 100% (95-145%) free triplet formation out of a maximum possible yield of 200%. A second method (ESI section 8.2.2) using ZnTPP as a reference at low excitation powers, gave rise to a free triplet yield of $72 \pm 17\%$ at 700 ns. Finally, combining the measured spot size with the triplet molar extinction coefficient gave a yield of 120-140% at 8 ns (ESI section 8.2.3). Considering that the TT state signal at 8 ns then decays to half its intensity over the next 100 ns, the actual free triplet yield would correspond to ~70% if one assumes that the molar extinction coefficient of the TT state is roughly twice that of a free triplet. However, reports suggest that the extinction coefficient of the TT state is typically less than twice that of the free triplet, and depends strongly on the strength of the coupling in the pair state.^{43,44} Thus, the free triplet yield in this case would be slightly higher than 70%, consistent with the other estimates.

Figure 3: (a) Time profiles of **Tcdimer** (15 μM) at 525 nm with increasing concentrations of **TCAQ** in THF, with a collision rate of $1.45 \times 10^9 \text{M}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ at 4mM **TCAQ**. The collision rate is calculated as per the equation $k_{TT} = k_{TT}^0 + k_c[Q]$, with k_{TT} as the decay of the triplet pair in the presence of quencher, k_{TT}^0 represents the decay of the unquenched triplet pair, k_c represents collision rate, $[Q]$ is the concentration of the quencher. The colored dashed lines show the expected triplet intensity based on the quenching efficiency. (b) The time profiles of **Tcdimer** (10 μM) at 600 nm with increasing concentrations of **ChI** in PhCN. The collision rate up to 100 μM was calculated to be $2 \times 10^8 \text{M}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ (details provided in SI, figure S3). (c) The corresponding nsTA spectra of **Tcdimer** with increasing concentrations of **ChI** in PhCN at 10 μs . (d) Scheme showing a possible mechanism of oxidative quenching from the TT state with pathways for charge recombination and charge separation.

Together, these approaches consistently suggest a free triplet yield less than or close to 100%. These yield measurements were conducted in toluene; however, as both the dynamics and the final triplet intensity are nearly identical in THF (tables S3, S4 and figure S29b and S32), we infer that the triplet yields are effectively the same in both solvents. However, in PhCN we see the triplet intensity becomes approximately 27% of the initial intensity (Figure 2c). The triplet yield in this case was found to be $33 \pm 8.2\%$ at 700 ns using ZnTPP as a reference (ESI Section 8.2.2).

Cyclic voltammetry of Tcdimer. To understand the redox properties and the potential for multi-electron redox activity we use cyclic voltammetry. As can be seen in the cyclic voltammograms in Figure 2e and Figure S23, there is no additional peak associated to multiple redox events of **Tcdimer** compared to **Tcmonomer**. We thus infer weak electronic coupling between the Tc units of **Tcdimer**, which is supported by calculations, *vide infra*. Importantly, the ratio of the integrated areas of the reduction waves of the Tc unit is approximately 1:2 for **Tcmonomer:Tcdimer**. This indicates that the Tc units in **Tcdimer** behave like two independent monomers, similar to what has been reported for **Tc-BP-Tc**.²⁷ This also suggests that for these dimers, multi-redox events could be performed at the same potential, which could be beneficial for multi-ET reactions.

ET studies using Tcdimer

ET from the TT state. Since the TT state of **Tcdimer** persists for up to 100 ns, we investigate whether it can take part in ET reactions

or not. The acceptor 11,11,12,12-tetracyano-9,10-anthraquinodimethane (**TCAQ**) can undergo concerted two-electron reduction,⁴⁵ making it a suitable acceptor to investigate two ET from the TT state of SF dimers. In our case, however, **TCAQ** does not significantly quench the free T_1 state significantly, (Figure S40a). This is consistent with the positive value of ΔG_{PET} (table 1). However, since SF in tetracene is isothermal, and if we assume that the TT state energy is close to that of the S_1 state, driving force calculations suggest **TCAQ** can quench the TT state of **Tcdimer**.

Table 1: Estimated driving force for ET from/to the T_1 and TT state of the **Tcdimer** to the quencher and if it is observed or not.

Quencher	ΔG in eV ^a (T_1 , substrate)	ΔG in eV (TT, substrate)	T_1 Quenching	TT Quenching
4F-TCNQ	-0.67, 0.0	-1.67, -0.98	Yes	No
ChI	-0.12	-1.12	Yes	No
DIPEA	0.92	-0.08	No	Yes
TCAQ	0.48, 1.36	-0.52, 0.36	No	Yes
TTF	0.36, 0.66	-0.64, -0.34	No	Yes

^aDriving force for the first ET, and where quenchers can accept/donate a second electron the driving force for this transfer is listed as a second value.

Indeed, quenching of the TT signal is observed in the nsTA experiments with increasing concentrations of **TCAQ** in THF (Figure 3a). No spectral evolution is observed during quenching (Figure S42b and Figure S42c), suggesting no formation of long-lived charge separated species, with the remaining signal corresponding to the free triplet spectra.

Interestingly, the long-lived triplet signal that remains after TT quenching is significantly larger than what would be expected from the quenching efficiency. For example, with 4 mM **TCAQ**, the signal at 525 nm (corresponding to the TT and T₁ ESA), shows a reduction in TT lifetime from 107 ns to 66 ns. The quenching efficiency (QE) can be calculated from the following equation:

$$QE = 1 - \frac{\tau}{\tau_0}$$

Where τ_0 is the lifetime in the absence of any quencher (in this example, 107 ns) and τ is the lifetime in the presence of the quencher (in this example, 66 ns). This yields a QE of ~40%, which means that ~60% of the TT are unquenched. Upon quenching, the Tc–Tc⁺ species is formed, which quickly recombines to the ground state and does not contribute to the triplet signal. Therefore, the remaining signal arise solely from the unquenched TT population. In THF, where the TT signal is reduced to 50% of its initial value (Figure 2c and Figure 3a), the expected signal at 525 nm should be ~30% of the initial intensity (i.e., half of the ~60% unquenched TT population, as indicated by the dashed lines in Figure 3a). However, the experimentally observed signal in Figure 3a is closer to 40% of the initial intensity. The same feature, a larger proportion of T₁ signal than expected based on TT quenching, is observed with 16 mM **TCAQ** and during quenching with electron donors **TTF** and **DIPEA**. (Figure S40 and Table S9). The calculations for the expected signal intensity are shown in Figure S41).

Since the TT state forms within 200 ps, the quenching observed on the nanosecond timescale is attributed to the TT state rather than the S₁. Furthermore, since ET from/to T₁ is energetically uphill (see ESI section 9), we rule out the possibility of single ET from the TT state leaving behind one unquenched triplet state. In other words, ET leading to tripletpair separation and oxidation of one tetracene unit is implausible in this case. On the other hand, CT from the TT state could result in complete quenching of the triplets, as shown in Figure 3d, suggesting that the TT state behaves as a singlet state in this case.

Now we turn to discuss why the quenching with these (**TCAQ**, **TTF** and **DIPEA**) electron and hole acceptors in THF and toluene does not result in any observable long-lived charge-separated species (Figure S42). Both one- and two-electron reduced **TCAQ** have absorption features within our detection window (400–700 nm),^{46,47} indicating that charge-separated species are not formed efficiently. Together with this observation, we also see an unexpectedly high remaining triplet signal. To rationalize this behaviour, we propose the following explanation (Figure 3d). Once the quencher diffuses to the TT excited **Tcdimer**, they first form a CT encounter complex. The CT encounter complex can be singlet or triplet in nature and since they lie close in energy, can interconvert through intersystem crossing. Since no charged species are observed, yet quenching is significant, the recombination within the CT

encounter complex must be efficient before diffusional separation occurs. Such recombination from the singlet CT complex could yield the ground state species. Recombination from the triplet CT complex can result in CT enhanced ISC to reform T₁.^{48–51} Fast CT recombination would yield no or few long-lived charge-separated species and, if the formation of T₁ is non-negligible, would explain the observed high triplet signal. In this case, quenching from TT resembles ET from a photoexcited singlet state with a maximum of 100% ET yield.

Thus, we also looked into the ET from **Tcmonomer** and **TIPS-Tc** to **TCAQ** and **TTF** (Figures S43–S46). At high **TCAQ** concentrations (16 mM), the S₁ states of **Tcmonomer** and **TIPS-Tc** are both quenched efficiently, yet no significant amount of charge-separated species was observed. With **TCAQ** and **TIPS-Tc** there was no increased triplet formation, indicating negligible reformation of T₁ (see ESI for details). Quenching of **Tcmonomer** with **TCAQ** also shows lower triplet yields, yet not to the extent of S₁ quenching, suggesting some amount of CT enhanced ISC. Experiments with **TTF** also suggest possible charge recombination (CR) to form T₁. Hence, we conclude that CR to form T₁ is a plausible explanation for the increased T₁ signal observed. Our results suggest that the TT state behaves similarly to the S₁ state (i.e., maximum 100% ET yield) when quenched by **TCAQ**, **TTF**, and **DIPEA**. Hence, SF dimers with relatively long-lived TT states can be used as a way of increasing the lifetime of singlet reactivity. It is challenging to unambiguously determine if ET proceeds from the TT or S₁ state since they are in equilibrium. Consequently, ET from the S₁ state would also leads to quenching of the TT state. Our results still suggest that the TT/S₁ equilibrium effectively prolongs the lifetime of this reactivity which differs from free triplet reactivity.

ET from the T₁ state. Next, we studied ET from the free triplets by using Chloranil (**Chl**) as the electron acceptor. In THF, quenching of the triplets was not observed (Figure S47); hence, a more polar solvent, PhCN, was used to stabilize the charged products. Figure 3b shows the triplet lifetime getting quenched with increasing concentrations of **Chl**. At higher concentrations (> 100 μM), the triplet decay becomes biexponential. This might arise from some pre-associated populations or from some TT states that could also take part in the ET. If the latter

were the case, then the second ET would be slower due to the already existing charge on the dimer.²⁶ While this remains a possible explanation, we cannot confirm it. In any case, the overall ET yield determined below indicates that such double reduction is, if present, only minor.

In contrast to the TT state quenching reported above for **TCAQ**, in the case of **ChI**, we see clear spectral evolution (Figure 3c). The decrease in triplet ESA is accompanied by the concomitant rise of the **ChI** radical anion at 450 nm. Using ZnTPP as a reference at low excitation powers, we determined the ET yield at 720 μM concentration of **ChI** to be $35 \pm 7.1\%$. This agrees well with the free triplet yield of Tcdimer in PhCN (calculations given in SI, figure S38). We also see no visible quenching of the TT state at this concentration, (Figure S48), supporting the claim that we are quenching only the free triplets in this case. Hence this corroborates the finding that the TT state gives rise to only one free triplet (see ESI section 11.1 for more details). In **Tc-BP-Tc**, the other covalently linked SF Tc dimer, the reported ET yield is $(170 \pm 10)\%$.²⁷ We therefore closely look into its photophysics on the ns timescale and compare it with that of **Tcdimer**.

Photophysical properties and ET behaviour of Tc-BP-Tc

Transient absorption and EPR. Figure 4a shows the nsTA spectra of **Tc-BP-Tc** in THF when excited at 543 nm. It is similar to the spectra reported in PhCN²⁷ with the characteristic triplet ESA bands in the 500-520 nm range. On probing the triplet ESA band at 520 nm (Figure 4b), we find that the signal intensity becomes $\sim 35\%$ of the initial value within 400 ns and then persists for 240 μs . In PhCN, the signal at the plateau becomes 20% of its initial signal intensity and then decays with the same time constant of 240 μs . This also resembles the kinetic traces previously reported.²⁷ From these observations, we conclude that the TT state of **Tc-BP-Tc** lives for up to 400 ns, almost 4 times longer than in **Tcdimer**, before recombining to form a single free T_1 . We note that the reported triplet yield of $180 \pm 10\%$ for **Tc-BP-Tc** was determined at early times ($\sim 1\text{ns}$), which refers to triplets in the triplet pair.²⁷ The greater loss of triplet signal, *i.e.*, a decrease to 35% triplet signal compared to 50% in **Tcdimer** in THF, could be because of multiple pathways of recombination occurring within the TT, *e.g.*, ^1TT to S_0S_0 in addition to ^1TT (*via* ^5TT to ^3TT) to T_1 .^{40,42}

tr-EPR measurements, performed at 80 K, confirm the existence of a ^5TT state, Figure 4c. Furthermore, modelling of the tr-EPR suggests strong coupling in the **Tc-BP-Tc** dimer, consistent with electronic structure calculations identifying stable conformers that exhibit Tc-Tc stacking (Figure S68 and ESI section 14), possibly explaining the increased ^1TT to S_0 decay. The ^5TT state is observed for several to tens of microseconds, and there is no evidence for the formation of spin-polarised free triplets, from either ISC or separation of the ^5TT state. The characteristic spectral shape, which is reproduced by simulations, arises when the eigenstates of the coupled triplet pair are populated according to their singlet character. This results in a population of the ^5TT state, where the populations of the magnetic sublevels display a complex dependence on the

Figure 4: (a) nsTA spectra of **Tc-BP-Tc** (10 μM) in THF excited at 543 nm. (b) The corresponding time profile of **Tc-BP-Tc** at 520 nm in THF. Also shown in the figure are the time profiles at 525 nm in PhCN. (c) Transient EPR measurement on **Tc-BP-Tc**, recorded at 80 K, the spectrum is integrated over 0.4-0.5 μs after photoexcitation. For the simulation details, refer to ESI.

relative orientation of the molecule, and thereby its ZF interaction matrices, and the magnetic field, B_0 . The presence of this population scheme, as far as we are aware, has only previously been unambiguously demonstrated in a limited

Figure 5: (a) Time profiles of **Tc-BP-Tc** (15 μM) at 520 nm with increasing concentrations of **TCAQ** in THF when excited at 543 nm. The collision rate at 4mM **TCAQ** was found to be $9.61 \times 10^8 \text{M}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$. The coloured dashed lines show the expected triplet intensity based on the quenching efficiency. (b) nsTA spectra of **Tc-BP-Tc** (15 μM) in PhCN with increasing concentrations of **4F-TCNQ** at 1 μs , when excited at 548 nm. The inset shows the corresponding time profiles at 520 nm. The collision rate in this case was found to be $6 \times 10^9 \text{M}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ (calculations provided in SI, figure S53).

number of intra-molecular SF materials and, although not fully understood, is proposed to arise in systems that display a fluctuating but large, relative to the ZF interaction, exchange interaction.^{52–56}

Low temperature (100 K) nsTA for **Tc-BP-Tc** in MeTHF (Figure S54) indicates that the initial decay component, assigned to triplet pair decay, is extended to 3.5 μs , compared to 400 ns at RT measurements. This time-scale is similar to the time scale of ^5TT decay of **Tc-BP-Tc** in the tr-EPR spectra.

ET from Tc-BP-Tc. Quenching of the TT state of **Tc-BP-Tc** with **TCAQ** (Figure 5a) resulted in no spectral evolution, yet a significant reduction of TT lifetime was observed, just as with **Tcdimer**. Here too the triplet signal is slightly greater than expected based on the TT quenching efficiency at 16 mM **TCAQ**, possibly due to CR to form T_1 , but the enhancement is not as pronounced as in **Tcdimer** (Table S14 and Figure S52).

Next, we look at the quenching of free T_1 using **Chl** in PhCN. As previously seen with the **Tcdimer**, we see spectral evolution

with the decay in triplet ESA followed by the corresponding rise at 450 nm due to the **Chl** radical anion. However, unlike the case of **Tcdimer** (where triplet absorption is negligible at 450 nm, the wavelength used to monitor the differential absorption of the reduced chloranil anion), **Tc-BP-Tc** exhibits considerable overlapping absorption at this wavelength making it challenging to accurately determine the yield. Hence, we conducted quenching experiments with another electron acceptor, 2,3,5,6-Tetrafluoro-7,7,8,8-tetracyanoquinodimethane (**4F-TCNQ**). Unlike the reduced **Chl** radical anion, whose absorption overlaps with that of the **Tc-BP-Tc** triplet ESA, the reduced **4F-TCNQ** anion exhibits distinct features in the near infrared at 760 nm and 850 nm (Figure 5b). Since the triplet ESA shows no signals in this region, the overlap is negligible, allowing for a cleaner and more reliable estimate of the triplet yield. Our results around 400 μM concentration of **4F-TCNQ** give an ET yield of $45 \pm 10\%$ (see ESI, S11.2, for more details). At this concentration, all the triplets have been quenched and what remains is the TT decay (Figure 5b, inset). The ET yield is in sound agreement with the observation that we see only about 20% of the initially formed triplets (180%)²⁷ in PhCN (Figure 4b). Hence, determining the ET yield at 100% T_1 quenching is another approach of determining the free triplet yield in this dimer. Overall, these results are coherent with the observation that the TT state gives rise to only a single free triplet, which is then quenched on the microsecond timescale.

Possibilities and limitations of SF dimers in multi-ET reactions

Our findings highlight a well-known limitation of covalently linked SF dimers for multielectron reactions; the correlated triplet pair (TT), confined to adjacent chromophores, has a high probability of recombination. This leads to reduced free-triplet yields, which undermines their potential for applications. A common strategy to address this limitation is the incorporation of additional repeating units. Increasing the oligomer length facilitates spatial separation of the triplet pair, enabling formation of the weakly correlated state ($^1\text{T} \dots \text{T}$) that mediates free-triplet generation. Such behaviour has been demonstrated in trimers, tetramers, and hexamers, where the triplet yield rises markedly with increasing oligomer size.^{38,57–59}

Another possibility is to directly link the electron acceptor with the SF dimer, which would enable intramolecular ET and override the diffusion limit. In this case, it might even be possible to extract two electrons directly from the TT state, which has also been looked into recently.³¹ The possibility for such a mechanism is suggested by experimental observations of triplet energy transfer directly from the triplet pair state.⁴² We investigated the possibility of such a stepwise two-ET through electronic structure calculations (See section 14 in the ESI for full details). Using the reported materials as an example, we find that both electron acceptors **Chl** and **TCAQ** preferentially interact with the tetracene backbone through π - π stacking interactions, which facilitate ET (Figure S64 and S65). In the **Tcdimer-TCAQ** system, quenching of an individual triplet from the TT state is energetically unfavourable as the CT state lies significantly higher in energy (Table S17). In this case, the CT

state and the triplet-pair state are energetically close, consistent with single-ET leading to the formation of the Tc-Tc⁺-Q⁻ encounter complex, as described above in Figure 3d. In contrast, in the **Tcdimer-Chl** and **Tc-BP-Tc-Chl** dyads, the CT state is nearly degenerate with the localized triplet state on one of the Tc moieties, possibly enabling the quenching of an individual triplet from the TT state for ¹Tc^{*}-Tc⁺ + Q⁻ (See section 14 in the ESI for full details). Experimentally, however, we see no evidence for this in both **Tc-BP-Tc** and **Tcdimer**. With 400 μM of **4F-TCNQ** and full quenching of the T₁ signal, the fast decay that we assign to TT decay is not quenched (Figure 5b, inset). This suggests that no ET occurs from the TT state to **4F-TCNQ**. It is possible that the strong coupling of the TT state observed for **Tc-BP-Tc** hinders such ET. Interestingly, we also see no evidence for ET from TT as if it behaved as a singlet state, forming Tc-Tc⁺-Q⁻. The driving force for this single ET is of the same order as that for single ET from the TT in **Tcdimer** to **4F-TCNQ**, around -1.7 eV (Table 1), which likely lies in the Marcus-inverted region. Further studies to fully understand these observations are needed. Similar observations can also be seen in the case of **Tcdimer**, where the TT remains unquenched at 720 μM of **Chl**. (Figure S48).

Another issue that must be understood for SF dimers to be applied to multi-ET reactions, is the fate of the remaining triplet after the first ET occurs. Hetzer *et al.* reported that in their pentacene dimer and tetramer, ET from one triplet quickly leads to loss of the remaining triplet through radical-enhanced ISC (RE-ISC), as they observe half of the expected ET yield.⁶⁰ However, in their analysis they have not considered the 50% loss of signal when assigning evolution-associated spectra to TT and T₁+T₁. A 50% loss in signal is similar to that observed by us and others^{38–42} (Figure 2c and 4b), and indicates loss of one triplet, *i.e.*, TT → T₁+S₀. If re-interpreted as such, the ET yield reported by Hetzer *et al.* would be consistent with efficient CT from the remaining T₁. It is, thus, still unclear how problematic RE-ISC might be in SF-based ET schemes.

Conclusions

Herein, we have, in detail, studied ET from two Tc-based SF dimers on timescales spanning both the singlet state-TT equilibrium and triplet states. This was performed by employing electron and hole acceptors with varying driving forces for ET to or from the TT and triplet states. Our results show that the TT state behaves analogously to a singlet when the quencher it encounters has sufficient driving force to quench the singlet state, enabling electron-transfer reactions that benefit from the prolonged reactivity associated with singlet character. Moreover, we demonstrate that because the TT state recombines to yield a single T₁ in these dimers, achieving an electron-transfer yield exceeding 100% in diffusion-limited reactions is inherently challenging. Drawing on these conclusions, the possibilities and limitations of multi-ET reactions using these systems have been discussed. These are key considerations needed to design next-generation SF chromophores for applications in solar cells and photoredox catalysis.

Author contributions

S.C. carried out the steady-state and transient spectroscopic measurements (fsTA and nsTA), performed data analysis, contributed to the mechanistic interpretation and writing of the manuscript. C.P. carried out the syntheses of the molecules involved, planning of the research and contributed to the writing and reviewing of the manuscript. A.J.R. carried out the tr-EPR measurements and the corresponding data analysis and writing of the manuscript. C.T. carried out the theoretical calculations. C.T. and D.C. designed the computational study, analysed the results, and contributed to the writing and reviewing of the manuscript. S.R. guided the tr-EPR measurements and contributed to the reviewing of the manuscript. V.G. conceived the research idea, devised both the synthetic and spectroscopic studies, guided the mechanistic interpretation and contributed to the writing of the manuscript.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Data availability

Additional experimental details, data and details for the synthesis, additional spectroscopic data (TCSPC, transient absorption), details on triplet and electron yield calculations, and additional computational details and results are available in the ESI.† Data underlying the figures and conclusions in this publication is available at Zenodo data repository at: [link to be added during proof](#)

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Additional experimental details, data and details for the synthesis, additional spectroscopic data (TCSPC, transient absorption), details on triplet and electron yield calculations, and additional computational details and results are available in the ESI.† Data underlying the figures and conclusions in this publication is available at Zenodo data repository at: “LINK TO BE ADDED IN PROOF”

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Electronic Supplementary Information for: Electron transfer from singlet fission dimers: possibilities and limitations†

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1. General Information

All reagents and solvents were purchased from Aldrich, Fluorochem or TCI Europe and used as received without further purification. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra were determined at room temperature in 5 mm o.d. tubes on a Bruker Avance 400 spectrometer of the Spectropole: ^1H (400 MHz) and ^{13}C (100 MHz). The ^1H chemical shifts were referenced to the solvent peak CDCl_3 (7.26 ppm) and the ^{13}C chemical shifts were referenced to the solvent peak CDCl_3 (77 ppm). **Tc-BP-Tc** dimer was synthesized as previously reported in the literature,¹ without modification and in similar yields.

1.1 Spectroscopic measurements

Unless specified otherwise, the samples were prepared inside an argon glovebox with oxygen levels below 10 ppm. The solvents were obtained from a Solvent Purification System (SPS) from Inert and then freeze pump thawed before bringing them inside the glovebox. The steady state UV-visible absorption was performed using Agilent Cary 5000 and the steady-state fluorescence spectra were obtained using Fluorolog 3-222 emission spectrophotometer (Horiba Jobin-Yvon). Spectra were acquired with FluorEssence software using a right-angle detector geometry (90° angle) along with corrections for variations in the lamp output and detector response. Fluorescence quantum yields were measured using Rhodamine 6G in ethanol $\phi_F = 0.95$ as the reference.² Time-resolved fluorescence measurements were carried out using FS5 system (Edinburgh instruments). The samples were excited using the picosecond pulsed light-emitting diode (ELED) at 470 nm. The measurement range was 200 ns with the peak preset at 10^4 counts in 1024 channels. The IRF was recorded using dilute LUDOX solution in de-ionized water at 470 nm excitation.

1.1.1 Nanosecond transient absorption (nsTA) measurements

The nsTA measurements were carried out using a Nd:YAG laser (Ekspla, NT342B laser) as the source of excitation of the samples with an OPO set at 545 nm having energies of 7-9 mJ/pulse. The spectrometer (LP920, Edinburgh Instruments) comprises of a pulsed 450 W ozone-free Xe arc lamp, a symmetrical Czerny-Turner monochromator (TMS300) with 5 nm bandwidth and detectors for both single kinetic traces (LP900 photomultiplier, with Tektronix TDS3012C oscilloscope) and entire spectra (Andor SH720 ICCD camera). The kinetic traces were fit using Origin.

1.1.2 Femtosecond transient absorption (fsTA) measurements

The fsTA measurements were carried out using a Ti:sapphire-based amplifier along with an integrated oscillator and pump lasers (Coherent Libra). A beam splitter splits the laser fundamental (800 nm, 3 kHz, fwhm 40fs) into a pump and probe which were then directed towards the UV-vis-NIR TA spectrometer (TAS, Newport Corp.). Optical parametric amplifiers (TOPAS NirUVVis, Light Conversion) were used to generate the excitation wavelength (pump-500 nm). The pump was passed through a waveplate that was set at magic angle and attenuated using a neutral density filter before reaching the sample. A calcium fluoride crystal was used to generate the probe supercontinuum (UV-vis) and an optical delay ($t_{\text{window}} \leq 8$ ns) was used to vary the path, thereby recording the transient spectra at varying pump-probe delay times on a silicon diode array (Newport custom-made). The samples were kept in 1 mm quartz cuvettes and had an absorbance of 0.2-0.3 at 500 nm. A pump power of 1mW was used for the measurements and focused on the sample in an approximately 0.05 mm² spot. The TA datasets were background and chip corrected using SurfaceXplorer software.

1.1.3 Transient electron paramagnetic resonance measurements (tr-EPR) and pulsed EPR

Sample Preparation: For the EPR measurements the tetracene compounds were prepared as toluene solutions, having a UV-Vis absorbance of 0.2-0.3 in a 2 mm cuvette. The solutions were loaded into 3.8 mm outer-diameter and 3 mm inner-diameter clear-fused quartz tubes (QSIL Ilmasil PN). The samples were rapidly frozen in liquid nitrogen prior to spectrometer insertion—a glassy solid was confirmed by visual inspection.

Tr-EPR: LASER excitation at 544–548 nm, as indicated, was provided by an Ekspla NT230 series tuneable diode-pumped LASER system at a repetition of 50 Hz (pulse duration ≈ 5 ns). Excitation energies were ≈ 1 mJ/pulse incident on the optical window of the cryostat. After the last turning mirror, the light was depolarised using an achromatic depolariser. A Stanford Research Systems digital delay generator (DG645) was used for synchronisation of the LASER system and EPR spectrometer (SpecJet TRIG IN). Transient EPR experiments were performed at the X-band on a Bruker ELEXSYS E580 spectrometer equipped with a critically coupled Bruker ER-4118X-MD5-W1 dielectric resonator. The experiments were performed at 80 K, using liquid nitrogen in combination with a continuous-flow cryostat (CF935, Oxford Instruments) and temperature controller (ITC4, Oxford Instruments). The data were acquired by direct-detection with the transient recorder (SpecJet-II digitiser) without lock-in amplification using a microwave power of 0.09–1.5 mW (corresponding to a attenuator settings of

32–20 dB). The data were acquired in cw mode using the diode standard pre-amplifier output with acAFC; the signal was amplified using a Stanford Research Systems low-noise voltage preamplifier (SR560) in a 3 kHz–1 MHz bandpass prior to entering the SpecJet Ch2 input. To minimise complicated background signals/artefacts, the trEPR experiments were acquired over several repeats/field sweeps, typically limiting the acquisition of each sweep to 15–20 min. The dataset repeats were acquired using the Python XeprAPI, saving the sweeps individually. The data were processed using lab-written Python routines. During dataset/repeat aggregation, the data were compensated for minor drifts in the mw frequency and interpolated along the field abscissa. The DC offset and LASER backgrounds were removed by two successive 1D baseline-corrections based in the pre-LASER time points as well as the low- and high-field off-resonance transients. The time abscissa was shifted to account for the LASER pulse position and the field abscissa was frequency-corrected to 9.75 GHz and calibrated with a standard carbon fibre sample, with a known g-factor ($g = 2.002\ 644$).³

Transient EPR simulations: These were performed in MATLAB using functions from the EasySpin package.^{4,5} The spectra were simulated using the pepper function. The **Tcmonomer** system was considered as a triplet state formed via spin–orbit coupling mediated intersystem crossing ($\text{spin_system.initState} = \{[\dots], 'xyz'\}$). The **Tc–BP–Tc** dimer system was considered as a pair of coupled triplets, for simplicity the spin Hamiltonian parameters of the individual triplets were taken from the **Tcmonomer** best fit parameters. It was found that, in general, simulations with a ferromagnetic coupling ($J > 0$, for $\hat{H}_{ex} = +JS_A^T S_B^T$) provided more faithful reproductions of the experimental spectrum; furthermore, it was found that the spectral changes observed for exchange couplings larger than approximately 120 GHz were modest. The triplet pair states were populated by their singlet character using the short-hand notation $\text{spin_system.initState} = 'singlet'$. For the **Tc–BP–Tc** simulations all interaction matrices were assumed to be collinear.

Table S1: Parameters for the tr-EPR simulations presented in the main text.

	Tcmonomer	Tc–BP–Tc
g_{iso}	2.0028	2.0028
$D_T, E_T / \text{MHz}$	[1412, –18.0]	[1412, –18.0]
$\text{dip}_{TT} / \text{MHz}$	-	[39.1, –45.6]
J_{TT} / GHz	-	263
initState	[0.468, 0.532, 0], 'xyz'	'singlet'
HStrain / MHz	[37.6, 22.5, 38.4]	[40.1, 27.2, 60.6]

Pulse EPR: Pulse EPR experiments were performed on a Bruker ELEXSYS E580 X-/Q-band spectrometer. Measurements were performed at the Q-band with a Bruker EN 5107-D2 resonator and a 50 W solid-state amplifier (Bruker) at a temperature of 80 K using liquid nitrogen with a continuous-flow cryostat and (Oxford Instruments CF935) and a temperature control system (Oxford Instruments ITC 4). The extent of resonator over-coupling was chosen to maximise sensitivity, balancing the excitation bandwidth and sufficiently minimising the ringing observed for the chosen τ -value. For pulse EPR measurements at the Q-band, the sample was excited through the top of the sample holder with depolarised light at 548 nm using an optical fibre with a diameter of 0.8 mm. The excitation energy was ≈ 0.5 mJ/pulse, measured at the fibre output, at a repetition rate of 50 Hz (pulse duration ≈ 5 ns).

An echo-detected field sweep was recorded using a two-pulse primary echo sequence with pulse lengths of $t_{\pi/2} = 12$ ns and $t_{\pi} = 24$ ns, an inter-pulse delay, τ , of 180 ns, and an echo integration gate of 80 ns. A two-step phase cycle, $[+(+x) - (-x)]$, was applied on the first pulse ((x)x). The mw pulse sequence was positioned 700 ns after the LASER pulse.

Field-dependent transient nutation measurements used the sequence $h\nu - \text{DAF} - \beta - \tau - t_{24} \text{ ns} - \tau - \text{echo}$. During the experiment the flip angle of the first pulse (β) was varied by increasing the pulse length in steps of 4 ns, starting at 12 ns. The mw pulse amplitudes were optimised to maximise the $p_{12} \text{ ns} - \tau - p_{24} \text{ ns}$ echo at circa 1208 mT, one of the field positions that displayed the highest nutation frequency. A four-step phase cycle $x[x]$ with linear combination coefficients +1, –1, +1, –1, i.e. $[+(+x) - (+y) + (-x) - (-y)]$ was used to remove unwanted signals, including possible contributions from the (–, –) pathway. Echo integration used an 80 ns gate, wide relative to the mw excitation, in an attempt to reduce off-resonance effects. The data were baseline corrected using a polynomial background function, apodised with a Hamming window, zero-filled

and the cross-term averaged FFT was calculated, with the absolute-value spectra presented. The frequency abscissa was normalised by division with a reference frequency obtained for a spin-1/2.

1.2 Cyclic voltammetry measurements

Cyclic voltammetry (CV) was performed using a 3 mm glassy carbon as the working electrode, a platinum wire counter electrode, Ag wire as the reference electrode and an AUTOLAB potentiostat (PGSTAT302). It was corrected for junction potentials by using the ferrocene couple (Fc⁺/Fc) as the internal reference. A solution of 0.1 M TBAPF₆ in THF containing the sample was purged with N₂ for 15 min after which the voltammograms were recorded.

1.3 UV-visible spectroelectrochemistry measurements

These were performed in a diode array spectrophotometer (Agilent 8453) using a quartz cell with a pathlength of 1 cm having pencil lead electrodes with reticulated vitreous carbon foam as the working and counter electrodes along with the Ag wire mentioned above as the reference electrode inside the glovebox. An AUTOLAB potentiostat (PGSTAT302) was used to perform controlled potential electrolysis of the sample and the time-resolved spectra was recorded.

2. Synthesis

2.1 Synthesis of Tcdimer:

The phenylacetylene linker **L-3** was synthesised in 3 steps from 2,5-dibromobenzene-1,4-diol. Brominated TIPS-tetracene **Tc-Br** was synthesized as described in the literature⁶ and coupling to the linker to form **Tcdimer** was done through Sonogashira coupling conditions.

2.1.1 Synthesis of L-1:⁷

In a 250 mL RBF, 2,5-dibromo-1,4-hydroquinone (5.36 g, 20 mmol, 1 eq.) was added followed by 100ml of acetone. K₂CO₃ (13.8 g, 0.1 mol, 5 eq.) was added to this suspension and stirred for 10 min. Then 13.8 mL (98 mmol, 5 eq.) of bromohexane were added and the mixture was refluxed overnight. Evaporation of the volatiles afforded a solid which was dissolved in ethyl acetate and washed twice with water then with brine. Filtration on silica followed by evaporation afforded a brown solid. It was then purified by column chromatography (silica gel, pentane/DCM, 5/1) yielding a white powder (3.72 g, 42% yield).

¹H NMR (400 MHz, Chloroform-D) δ 7.08 (s, 2H), 3.94 (t, J = 6.5 Hz, 4H), 1.85 – 1.76 (m, 4H), 1.53 – 1.44 (m, 4H), 1.34 (dq, J = 7.2, 3.6 Hz, 9H), 0.93 – 0.89 (m, 6H) ppm.

¹³C NMR (101 MHz, Chloroform-D) δ: 150.20, 118.57, 111.24, 70.41, 31.61, 29.21, 25.73, 22.70, 14.15 ppm.

Figure S2: ^{13}C NMR of **L-1** in CDCl_3

2.1.2 Synthesis L-2

To 1,4-dibromo-2,5-bis(hexyloxy)benzene (2 g, 6.76 mmol) was added Pd(PPh₃)₄ (64 mg, 0.09 mmol, 2 mol %), CuI (15 mg, 0.7 mmol, 4 mol %) and triisopropylsilylacetylene (3.7 mL, 16.5 mmol, 3.5 eq). NEt₃ (20 mL) was then added, and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 60 h under an inert Ar environment. After the reaction, the black mixture was evaporated and the crude residue was purified by column chromatography (pentane then DCM:pentane, 50:50) followed by a recrystallization in MeOH affording a yellow powder (2.35g, 55% yield).

¹H NMR (400 MHz) δ : 7.09 (s, 2H), 3.95 (t, J = 6.5 Hz, 4H), 1.84 – 1.76 (m, 4H), 1.52 – 1.44 (m, 4H), 1.39 – 1.29 (m, 8H), 0.91 (t, 6H) ppm.

¹³C NMR (101 MHz, Chloroform -D) δ : 154.14, 117.20, 114.12, 103.17, 96.30, 69.45, 31.79, 29.53, 25.93, 22.73, 18.79, 14.17, 11.46 ppm.

Figure S3: ¹H NMR of L-2 in CDCl₃

Figure S4: ^{13}C NMR of **L-2** in CDCl_3

2.1.3 Synthesis L-3:

The reactant (1 g, 1.56 mmol, 1 eq.) was dissolved in THF (200 mL) and a 1 M tetrabutylammonium fluoride was added to the solution (3.13 mL, 3.13 mmol, 2 eq.). The solution was stirred at room temperature for 1 h. The mixture was extracted with dichloromethane and washed with water (2 x 50 mL). The organic phase was dried with Na_2SO_4 and evaporated. The crude was then purified by column chromatography (Ethyl acetate: pentane, 2:8) to yield a yellow powder (68% yield).

^1H NMR (400 MHz, Chloroform- d) δ 6.94 (s, 2H), 3.95 (t, $J = 6.6$ Hz, 4H), 3.32 (s, 2H), 1.78 (dq, $J = 8.3, 6.7$ Hz, 4H), 1.50 – 1.43 (m, 4H), 1.36 – 1.29 (m, 8H), 0.91 – 0.85 (m, 6H) ppm.

^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, Chloroform- D) δ : 154.09, 117.82, 113.35, 82.55, 79.90, 69.77, 31.64, 29.20, 25.70, 22.71, 14.15 ppm.

Figure S5: ^1H NMR of **L-3** in CDCl_3

Figure S6: ^{13}C NMR of **L-3** in CDCl_3

2.1.4 Synthesis Tcdimer:

Tc-Br (204 mg, 0.3 mmol, 2 eq) was dissolved in 15 mL of dioxane. Once complete dissolution, $\text{Pd}(\text{Ph}_3)_4$ (10.5 mg, 0.01 mmol, 5 mol%) and CuI (1.5 mg, 0.02 mmol, 6 mol%) were added to the media, followed by 1,4-diethynyl-2,5-bis(hexyloxy)benzene (50 mg, 1 eq, 0.15 mmol) and 10 mL of triethylamine. The media was then heated at 80°C for 72 h, under inert Ar environment. After the reaction, the black mixture was evaporated to remove the solvent, followed by dissolution in DCM and washing with brine. The crude residue was purified by column chromatography (DCM:heptane, 2:8) to yield a dark red solid (129 mg, 56 % yield).

^1H NMR (400 MHz, Chloroform- d) δ : 9.28 (d, $J = 3.4$ Hz, 4H), 8.65 – 8.62 (m, 4H), 8.24 (s, 2H), 7.99 (d, $J = 8.9$ Hz, 2H), 7.59 – 7.56 (m, 4H), 7.56 (s, 1H), 7.54 (d, $J = 1.5$ Hz, 1H). δ 7.17 (s, 2H), 4.15 (t, $J = 6.5$ Hz, 4H), 1.96 (q, $J = 8.3, 6.5$ Hz, 4H), 1.62 (td, $J = 9.3, 8.5, 4.5$ Hz, 4H), 1.50 – 1.39 (m, 8H), 1.37 – 1.31 (m, 96H), 0.91 (t, $J = 7.1$ Hz, 6H) ppm.

^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, Chloroform -D) δ : 153.97, 132.95, 132.90, 132.21, 131.65, 131.15, 130.82, 130.78, 128.79, 128.31, 127.51, 127.01, 126.56, 126.48, 120.91, 118.84, 117.00, 114.17, 106.30, 106.13, 103.83, 96.01, 87.88, 69.81, 31.72, 29.41, 25.87, 22.79, 19.07, 19.05, 14.16, 11.68 ppm.

IR (cm^{-1}): 2960, 2940, 2860 (C-H: bending aromatic); 2145, 2120 (C-C triple bound : bending)

HRMS (MALDI-TOF) m/z : theor: 1498.91 found: 1499.917 ($[\text{M}]^+$ detected).

Figure S7: ^1H NMR of **Tcdimer** in CDCl_3

Figure S8: ^{13}C NMR of **Tcdimer** in CDCl_3

Figure S9: FTIR spectrum of **Tcdimer**

Figure S11: ¹H NMR of **Tcmonomer** in CDCl₃

Figure S12: ¹³C NMR of **Tcmonomer** in CDCl₃

Figure S13: HRMS (MALDI-TOF) results of **Tcmonomer**

2.2 Synthesis of Tc-BP-Tc:

For the biphenyl tetracene dimer **Tc-Br** was first converted to the boronic acid pinacolester following Sanders et al.⁶ and then used in a Suzuki coupling reaction with 2,2'-dibromobiphenyl following the procedure by Nakamura et al.¹

2.2.1 Synthesis of Tc-boronic acid pinacole ester (**Tc-BPin**):

Tc-Br (1.0 g, 1.5 mmol), bis(pinacolato)diboron (0.6 ml, 2.3 mmol), Pd(dppf)Cl₂(DCM) (60 mg, 0.07 mmol) and KOAc (0.52 g, 5.3 mmol) was added to a dry Schlenk tube. The tube was degassed by sequential vacuum and N₂, followed by the addition of dry and degassed dioxane (7 ml). The mixture was heated to 85 °C overnight in the dark. The reaction mixture was transferred to 50 mL DCM and washed with water. The aqueous layer was extracted with DCM (50 mL). The combined organic phase was dried over Na₂SO₄, filtered and solvent removed under reduced pressure. The crude reaction mixture was purified by silica column chromatography using a mixture of hexanes and DCM as eluent to yield 715 mg (32% yield) of bright red product. Spectroscopic data conformed to literature.⁶

¹H NMR (400 MHz, Chloroform-d) δ: 9.32 (s, 1H), 9.27 (s, 1H), 8.66 – 8.60 (m, 2H), 8.55 (s, 1H), 7.96 (d, J = 8.6 Hz, 1H), 7.78 – 7.74 (m, 1H), 7.56 – 7.51 (m, 2H), 1.43 (s, 12H), 1.34 – 1.30 (m, 38H) ppm.

Figure S14: ^1H NMR of *Tc-Bpin* in CDCl_3

2.2.2 Synthesis of *Tc-BP-Tc*:

Tc-BPin (200 mg, 0.28 mmol), 2,2'-dibromobiphenyl (29.4 mg, 0.094 mmol), $\text{PdCl}_2(\text{dppf}) \cdot \text{DCM}$ (40 mg, 0.05 mmol), and K_2CO_3 (664 mg, 4.480 mmol) were transferred to a Schlenk flask and the atmosphere exchanged for N_2 through repeated vacuum and N_2 . Deaerated THF (30 mL) and deaerated H_2O (3 mL) was added to the flask. The reaction mixture was purged with N_2 for an additional 20 min and then stirred for 25 h at 70°C in the dark. After cooling to room temperature, the reaction was extracted with DCM and washed with water, the organic phase was dried over Na_2SO_4 and solvent was removed by evaporation. The obtained crude was purified by silica gel column chromatography using mixture of hexane and DCM as an eluent (hexane/DCM = 20/1, v/v). The product was purified by recrystallization and 70 mg (55%) was obtained as a red powder. HRMS, UV-Vis and transient absorption spectra conformed to expected and reported data, however ^1H NMR did not match that reported by Nakamura et al, and the reported ^{13}C -NMR is very noisy rendering comparison difficult.¹ However, our ^1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR together with COSY-NMR strongly agree with the suggested dimer structure (see assignment and figures S15-S18 below). In the ^{13}C 31 signal could be found which is 1 less than expected. It is likely that the signal at 130.51 ppm is an overlay of two signals since its intensity is significantly higher than for other aromatic signals.

^1H NMR (400 MHz, Chloroform- d) δ : 9.15 (s, 2H), 8.86 (s, 2H), 8.68 – 8.47 (m, 4H), 7.59 (d, J = 9 Hz, 2H), 7.55 – 7.48 (m, 6H), 7.42 – 7.31 (m, 8H), 6.79 (dd, J = 9, 1.7 Hz, 2H), 1.29 (s, 42H), 1.12 (bs, 42H) ppm.

^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, Chloroform - D) δ : 140.66, 140.05, 138.56, 132.61, 132.56, 132.03, 132.00, 130.93, 130.51, 130.47, 128.75, 128.29, 127.89, 127.78, 127.75, 127.51, 127.43, 126.63, 126.59, 126.29, 125.69, 118.61, 118.52, 105.78, 105.69, 104.08, 103.82, 19.01, 18.91, 11.67, 11.53 ppm.

HRMS (MALDI-TOF):) m/z : theor: 1326.76791 found: 1326.76805 ($[\text{M}]^+$ detected).

Table S2. Assignment of ^1H -NMR peaks of Tc-biphenyl dimer as labeled in Figure S15, note the color coding.

Shift, ppm	Multiplicity	Coupling constant, Hz	Integral	Assignment
9.15	s		1	12
8.86	s		1	1
8.68-8.47	m		2	10, 7
7.59	d	9	1	3
7.55-7.48	m		3	9, 8 and 6 or 3
7.42-7.31	m		4	5, 4 and 6 or 3 and 5
(7.40)	s		1	5, visible in COSY only
6.79	dd	9, 1.7	1	4
1.29	bs		21	TIPS
1.12	bs		21	TIPS

Figure S15: Atom labeling of Tc-BP-Tc

Figure S18: COSY-NMR of *Tc-BP-Tc* in $CDCl_3$.

Figure S19 : HRMS (MALDI-TOF) results of *Tc-BP-Tc*

3. Uv-Vis absorption and fluorescence

Figure S20: (a) Normalised fluorescence spectra of **Tcdimer** in different solvents. (b) Time-resolved fluorescence decays of **Tcdimer** in different solvents (c) Normalised absorption and fluorescence of **Tcdimer** in THF, the 0-0 transition occurs at 551 nm. (d) Steady state absorption of **Tcdimer** in different solvents.

Table S3. Fluorescence quantum yields and lifetimes of **Tcdimer** in different solvents.

Solvent	F.L. QY (%)	Lifetimes (ns)	Relative amplitudes
Toluene	20.6 ± 2.4	6.29, 32.66, 101.52	0.57, 0.35, 0.069
THF	16.5 ± 1.6	6.44, 32.85, 104.73	0.63, 0.29, 0.065
PhCN	14.5 ± 1.2	6.2, 16.47, 105.04	0.44, 0.54, 0.0067

Figure S21: Time resolved fluorescence decays of **TIPS-Tc** (a) and **Tcmonomer** in THF. (b). Monoexponential fits yield lifetimes of (a) 12.8 ns and (b) 3.85 ns.

4. Electrochemistry

Cyclic voltammograms of **TCAQ**, and **Tcdimer** are shown in figures S22 and S23, respectively. The spectra of the reduced **Tcdimer** is shown in Figure S24.

Figure S22: Cyclic voltammetry of Tetracyanoantraquinone (**TCAQ**) in a) THF with 0.1M of TBAPF₆ b) DCM with 0.1M of TBAPF₆

Figure S23: Cyclic voltammetry of **Tcdimer** in THF with 0.1M of TBAPF₆Figure S24: Spectra of oxidized **Tcdimer** (600 μ M, cell length 1 cm) in THF. A potential of 0.8 V vs Fc⁺/Fc was applied to the solution and the change in spectra was recorded at different times.

5. fsTA data of Tcdimer and Tcmonomer

Figure S26: fsTA 2D map of **Tcdimer** in THF excited at 500 nm (left) and spectra at selected time points (right).

Figure S27: fsTA 2D map of **Tcdimer** in PhCN excited at 500 nm (left) and spectra at selected time points (right).

Figure S28: fsTA 2D map of **Tcmonomer** in THF excited at 500 nm (left) and spectra at selected time points (right).

6. Global Analysis of fsTA

R package TIMP and its GUI Glotaran was used to perform global analysis by the least-squares fitting method. A three component sequential model ($A \rightarrow B \rightarrow C$) based on a previous paper⁸ was used to fit the data. The evolution associated spectra (EAS) are shown in the main text and Figure S29. Based on the interpretation of Rapp *et al.*⁸ of a similar tetracene dimer we assign the intermediate component to a charge transfer intermediate $S_1S_0^{CT}$. This interpretation is supported by the faster formation of $S_1S_0^{CT}$ and subsequent slower 1TT formation in the polar solvent PhCN, Table S4. However, if the requirement of this intermediate in the fitting is indeed a result of a stepwise 1TT formation via a charge transfer state, or a result of rotational dynamics and populations of slightly different coupling is beyond the scope of the current investigation.

Figure S29: Three state EAS obtained from global analysis of the fsTA data of **Tcdimer** in (a) PhCN and (b) Toluene upon excitation at 500 nm.

Table S4: Time constants summarized from fitting by global analysis of fsTA data of **Tcdimer** in different solvents

Solvent	(S_1S_0) (ps)	$S_1S_0^{CT}$ (T_1T_1) (ps)	$^1(T_1T_1)$ (ns)
Toluene	19.2	188.7	87.1
THF	14.2	151.5	53.3
PhCN	11.2	515	22.9

Figure S30: (a) Two state EAS obtained from global analysis of the fsTA data of **Tcmonomer** in THF (b) Model used to fit the data, the values in red represent the time constants that were fitted and the value in black was kept fixed.

7. nsTA of Tcdimer

Figure S31: nsTA spectra of *Tcdimer* when excited at 545 nm in (a) Toluene (b) PhCN

Figure S32: nsTA kinetic profiles at 525 nm of *Tcdimer* in THF and Toluene, indicating similar final triplet intensity in both solvents.

Figure S33: The time profiles at 525 nm for **Tcdimer** and at 516 nm for **Tcmonomer** show that they decay with a similar time constant of 240 μs in THF.

8. Determination of the triplet yield of Tcdimer

These nsTA measurements were carried out in 1cm \times 1cm cuvette in toluene as the solvent. The calculation of triplet yield and triplet extinction coefficients was done at low powers, because at high powers of 6 mJ/pulse, the triplet decay of the zinc porphyrins (Zinc octaethyl porphyrin, ZnOEP, and Zinc tetraphenyl porphyrin, ZnTPP) was found to be biexponential due to triplet-triplet annihilation, Figure S34a. Hence the experiments were done at low powers of around 120 $\mu\text{J/pulse}$, where monoexponential decays were observed, Figure S34b, so that the triplet yield can be estimated more accurately.

Figure S34: (a) Time trace of ZnOEP at 430 nm when excited with 6.5 mJ/pulse at 572 nm. (b) Time trace of ZnOEP at 430 nm when excited with 120 $\mu\text{J/pulse}$ at 572 nm.

Table S5. Fits to triplet decay of ZnOEP at different excitation powers, as shown in Figure S32.

Power @ 572 nm	Type of exponential fit	Lifetimes (amplitude)
6 mJ/pulse	Biexponential	20.21 μs (75%) & 141.52 μs (25%)
120 $\mu\text{J/pulse}$	Monoexponential	424 μs

8.1 Determination of the triplet extinction coefficient:

For the measurement of the triplet extinction coefficient, the samples were excited at 570 nm. The concentration of the donor (ZnOEP) was 5 μM and the acceptor, **Tcdimer** was 20 μM . The extinction coefficient of the triplet excited state of the dimer was determined by using the energy transfer (EnT) method.¹ It can be described by the following equations:

Here, D is the energy donor which is ZnOEP and A is the acceptor which is **Tcdimer**. The energy transfer efficiency and related equations are:

$$\phi_{\text{EnT}} = \frac{k_{\text{EnT}}[A]}{(k_{\text{EnT}}[A] + k_{0,D})} \dots \dots \dots (\text{S1})$$

$$\varepsilon_{\text{A}} = \frac{\varepsilon_{\text{D}} \times \Delta \text{Abs}_{\text{A}}}{\Delta \text{Abs}_{\text{D}} \times \phi_{\text{EnT}}} \dots \dots \dots (\text{S2})$$

The molar extinction coefficient of ZnOEP at 570 nm was taken as 37,716 M⁻¹cm⁻¹ as obtained from <https://omlc.org/spectra/PhotochemCAD/html/050.html>. There is a non-zero molar extinction coefficient (6,199 M⁻¹cm⁻¹) around 545-550 nm but, at 500 ns, the delta absorbance of the donor at 545 nm was found to be zero because of the overlapping ESA. So, we took a value of 37,716 – 6,199 = 31,517 M⁻¹cm⁻¹ as the value of the molar extinction coefficient for the donor.

From the plots Figure S35(a) and (b) below the following rate constants were obtained:

$$k_{\text{A}} = 2,774 \text{ s}^{-1} \quad k_{0,D} = 3,060.81 \text{ s}^{-1} \quad k_{\text{EnT}}[A] = 16,436.16 \text{ s}^{-1}$$

From the spectra Figure S35 (c) the ΔAbs values of the donor and **Tcdimer** were obtained at 500 ns and 100 μs respectively.

$$\Delta \text{Abs}_{\text{D}} = 0.01 \text{ at } 570 \text{ nm}$$

$$\Delta \text{Abs}_{\text{A}} = 0.0042 \text{ at } 525 \text{ nm}$$

Substituting these values into equations (S1) and (S2), we get, $\phi_{\text{EnT}} = 0.843$ and ε_{A} at 525 nm to be 15,700 M⁻¹cm⁻¹.

Figure S35: (a) Time profile of the donor (ZnOEP) and that of the donor and **Tcdimer** mixture at 460 nm (b) Time profile of the donor and **Tcdimer** mixture at 525 nm with the inset showing the rise in few microseconds (c) Spectra of the donor and **Tcdimer** mixture: At 500 ns, the spectra mostly consist of the triplet state of ZnOEP and at 100 μs , the spectra mostly consist of the triplet state of **Tcdimer**.

8.2 Determination of the triplet yield in Tcdimer:

Above we have determined the ϵ_T to be $15,700 \text{ M}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$ at 525 nm. We have used three different methods to calculate the triplet yield using both the nsTA and fsTA setups.

8.2.1 Method I:

The spectral deconvolution method⁹ was used to calculate the triplet quantum yield of **Tcdimer** from the fsTA data in toluene. The spectra at timepoints (0.2-0.5 ps) and (200-300 ps) were chosen and assigned to the first excited singlet state (S_1) and the correlated triplet pair state (TT), Figure S36. Then the basis spectra for S_1 and TT were obtained by adding the above spectra to a scaled ground state absorption spectrum, respectively, till no peaks of the absorption spectrum can be seen. The basis spectrum of the ground state bleach (GSB) was taken to be the absorption spectrum scaled to a similar absorbance as of the delta absorbances in the fsTA data. These basis spectra (GSB, S_1 and TT) were then normalised to the GSB that they share (i.e. divided by the peak absorption of the ground state absorption spectra used), and then a linear regression was done on the experimental TA data using MATLAB to yield the time dependent populations associated with each basis spectrum that best reproduces the TA data.

We see a quantitative 1:1 conversion from the S_1 to the TT state as shown below (90-120 % TT yield), Figure S36e. Similar analysis was extended to the nsTA data. Spectra at 30 ns was assigned to the TT state and the spectra at 200 ns to the T_1 state, Figure S36b. The rest of the analysis is similar to the one carried out above. Here we see that the free triplet yield lies between 95-145 %, Figure S36f.

Figure S36. (a) fsTA spectra used to represent the S1 and TT TA spectra of **Tcdimer**. (b) nsTA spectra used to represent the TT and T1 TA spectra. (c) Obtained basis spectra for S1, TT and GSB on the fs time scale. (d) Obtained basis spectra for TT, T1 and GSB on the ns time scale. (e) Extracted population dynamics from spectral deconvolution of fsTA data using the basis spectra in (c). (f) extracted population dynamics from spectral deconvolution of nsTA data using the basis spectra in (d).

8.2.2 Method II:

Using ZnTPP as the reference because of its high triplet quantum yield (90%) and large triplet molar absorption coefficient ($78,000 \text{ M}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$ at 470 nm),¹⁰ the triplet quantum yield of the dimer was calculated according to the following equation (S3).

These nsTA measurements were carried out in 1cm×1cm cuvette in toluene as the solvent. The samples were excited at 545 nm at very low powers of 95 μJ/pulse so as to avoid the effects of the annihilation of the triplet excited states of the ZnTPP. The nsTA spectra were measured at a delay of 700 ns.

$$\phi_{T,dimer} = \frac{\Delta Abs_{dimer}}{\Delta Abs_{ZnTPP}} \times \frac{\epsilon_{T,ZnTPP}}{\epsilon_{T,dimer}} \times \frac{1-10^{-Abs_{545nm,ZnTPP}}}{1-10^{-Abs_{545nm,dimer}}} \times \phi_{T,ZnTPP} \dots \dots \dots (S3)$$

Here, ϕ_T , ϵ_T and ΔAbs and Abs stand for the quantum yield of the excited triplet states formed, the molar absorption coefficient of the triplet state, delta absorbance in nsTA at 700 ns and absorbance at 545 nm in the steady state measurement respectively. The values (summarized in Table S6) were obtained from the plots below (Figure S37 (a) and (b)) and substituted in equation (S3) to give the triplet quantum yield of **Tcdimer**. The triplet quantum yield of the dimer at 700 ns was determined to be $76 \pm 17\%$.

Figure S37: (a) Absorbance spectra of **Tcdimer** and ZnTPP in toluene (b) nsTA spectra of the above at 700 ns.

Table S6: Table summarizing the values used for determining the triplet yield of **Tcdimer** in toluene.

	ΔAbs at 700 ns	Abs at 545 nm	$\epsilon_T (M^{-1}cm^{-1})$	ϕ_T	$\Delta(\Delta Abs)$	$\Delta\epsilon_T (M^{-1}cm^{-1})$
ZnTPP	0.027 (470 nm)	0.35	78000	0.90	0.0007	8000
Tcdimer	0.005 (525 nm)	0.4	15700	0.72	0.0009	1613

Error calculation:

The error associated with the triplet yield calculation is described in equation (S4).

$$\frac{\Delta\phi_{T,dimer}}{\phi_{T,dimer}} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\Delta(\Delta Abs_{dimer})}{\Delta Abs_{dimer}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\Delta(\Delta Abs_{ZnTPP})}{\Delta Abs_{ZnTPP}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\Delta(\epsilon_{T,ZnTPP})}{\epsilon_{T,ZnTPP}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\Delta(\epsilon_{T,dimer})}{\epsilon_{T,dimer}}\right)^2} \dots \dots \dots (S4)$$

Considering the large uncertainty of the relative measurements, we believe the triplet yields are closer to 100% in the **Tcdimer**, as estimated by Method I.

Similarly, free triplet yield of Tcdimer in PhCN was calculated using the values provided in table S7 at 700 ns and the error calculated as per equation S4 to yield a value of $33.7 \pm 8.2\%$. The excitation wavelength was 550 nm with a power of 105 μJ/pulse. The plots used to get the values in table S7 are provided in Figure S38.

Figure S38: (a) Absorbance spectra of **Tcdimer in PhCN** and **ZnTPP in toluene** (b) nsTA spectra of the above at 700 ns.

Table S7: Table summarizing the values used for determining the triplet yield of **Tcdimer in PhCN**.

	ΔAbs at 700 ns	Abs at 550 nm	$\epsilon_T (M^{-1}cm^{-1})$	ϕ_T	$\Delta(\Delta Abs)$	$\Delta\epsilon_T (M^{-1}cm^{-1})$
ZnTPP	0.0067(470 nm)	0.066	78000	0.90	0.0005	8000
Tcdimer	0.0026(525 nm)	0.562	15700	0.32	0.0005	1613

8.2.3 Method III:

Alternatively, we measured the spot size of the beam in the fsTA setup and used it to calculate the concentration of the excited singlet states formed. The fraction of light intensity of the pump laser (excitation wavelength: 500 nm) passing through a solution (Tcdimer in toluene) in a cuvette can be calculated as follows:

$$\frac{I}{I_0} = 1 - 10^{-A(500\text{ nm})} = 1 - 10^{-0.32} = 1 - 0.48 = 0.52$$

To calculate photons/pulse, the laser power is divided by the energy per photon and half the repetition rate of the laser. The area of the pump pulse was determined with the help of a beam profiler which measured the major and minor diameters of the ellipse-shaped pulse (Figure S39), and the cuvette length was 1 mm.

We used two different methods to determine the radii of the spot size as the laser spot was not perfectly circular. In the first method, the entire overlapped region comprising the two major spots and the probe was considered as a single spot and then the radii were determined. In the second method, the above-mentioned spot was divided into two spots and then the radii were calculated by summing the radii of the two individual spots. So, we have then two volumes and hence, two singlet and triplet yields.

Power = 1 mW

Energy per photon = 3.975×10^{-19} J

Repetition rate of the laser = 3 kHz

$$\frac{\text{photons}}{\text{pulse}} = \frac{\text{laser power}}{(\text{energy per photon} \times 0.5 \times \text{repetition rate of laser})} = \frac{(1 \times 10^{-3} Js^{-1})}{3.975 \times 10^{-19} J \times 1.5 \times 10^3 s^{-1}} = 1.67 \times 10^{12}$$

- (i) Volume of the irradiated spot $V_1 = \pi \times r_1 \times r_2 \times d = 3.14 \times 192 \mu m \times 246.5 \mu m \times 0.1 \text{ cm} = 1.48 \times 10^{-7} L$ (one overlapped size)
- (ii) Volume of the irradiated spot $V_2 = \pi \times r_1 \times r_2 \times d = 3.14 \times 241.6 \mu m \times 232.5 \mu m \times 0.1 \text{ cm} = 1.76 \times 10^{-7} L$ (sum of two sizes)

Figure S39: (a) Beam profile of the 500 nm pump (b), (c) Dividing the area in (a) in two sections

The concentration of the singlet excited states can then be calculated as follows:

$$[S_1^1] = \frac{\left(\frac{\text{photons}}{\text{pulse}}\right) \times \frac{I}{I_0}}{N_A \times V_1} = \frac{(1.67 \times 10^{12} \times 0.52)}{(1.48 \times 10^{-7} \text{L} \times 6.02 \times 10^{23} \text{mol}^{-1})} = 9.74 \times 10^{-6} \text{M}$$

$$[S_1^2] = \frac{\left(\frac{\text{photons}}{\text{pulse}}\right) \times \frac{I}{I_0}}{N_A \times V_2} = \frac{(1.67 \times 10^{12} \times 0.52)}{(1.76 \times 10^{-7} \text{L} \times 6.02 \times 10^{23} \text{mol}^{-1})} = 8.19 \times 10^{-6} \text{M}$$

Using the triplet extinction coefficient the yield of the total number of triplets at 8 ns is then calculated as follows:

$$\phi_{T1}^1 = \frac{\left(\frac{\Delta Abs}{\epsilon_T \times d}\right)}{[S_1^1]} = \frac{(0.018)}{(15700 \times 0.1)} = 1.17$$

$$\phi_{T1}^2 = \frac{\left(\frac{\Delta Abs}{\epsilon_T \times d}\right)}{[S_1^2]} = \frac{(0.018)}{(15700 \times 0.1)} = 1.39$$

Considering that the triplets at 8 ns correspond to triplet-pairs, and that by 200 ns the signal is halved, the final yield of free triplets is half of the above calculated values, around 70%, similar to that estimated in Method II. However, the estimate in method III assumes that there is no change in the extinction coefficient of a triplet in the triplet pair compared to a free triplet. This assumption might not be fully accurate, and considering the general uncertainty in the extinction coefficients, we make a combined assessment using all determined yields (methods I-III) and find it likely that the yields lie in the interval 70-100 %.

9. Calculations of driving force for electron transfer

9.1 Oxidative quenching:

The reduction potentials of TCAQ (TCAQ/TCAQ^{•-} and TCAQ^{•-}/TCAQ⁻) obtained from its CV (Figure S22) are -0.96 V and -1.84 V vs Fc⁺/Fc respectively. For Tcdimer, the reduction and oxidation potential (vs Fc⁺/Fc) is estimated to be -1.64 V and 0.77 V respectively from its CV (Figure S23). These potentials are also similar to what has been reported for Tc-BP-Tc.¹ So, we can conclude that the driving force calculations should apply for Tc-BP-Tc as well.

Considering that the ¹TT state energy is similar to the S₁ state, we assume that it is roughly equal to 2.25 eV, based on the intersection point of the normalized absorption and fluorescence spectra (Figure S20). We can then calculate the oxidation potential of the ¹TT state using the below formula:

$$Eox_{TT}^* = Eox_{dimer} - E_{0,0}/e$$

$$Eox_{TT}^* = 0.77 \text{ V} - 2.25 \text{ V} = -1.48 \text{ V}$$

The oxidation potential of the triplet state of the dimer can be calculated if we assume the triplet state energy to be around 1.25 eV.^{11,12} Then we get,

$$Eox_{Triplet}^* = Eox_{dimer} - E_{0,0}/e$$

$$Eox_{Triplet}^* = 0.77 V - 1.25 V = -0.48 V$$

The driving force for electron transfer from the ¹TT state of the dimer to **TCAQ** can be calculated as per the following:¹³

$$\Delta G = -e(Ered_{TCAQ/TCAQ^{*-}} - Eox_{TT}^*)$$

$$\Delta G = -e(-0.96V - (-1.48V))$$

$$\Delta G = -0.52 eV$$

The negative Gibbs free energy change suggests that the electron transfer from the TT state of the dimer to the ground state of **TCAQ** to yield **TCAQ^{•-}** is feasible.

The driving force for electron transfer from the triplet state of the dimer to **TCAQ** can be calculated as per the following:

$$\Delta G = -e(Ered_{TCAQ/TCAQ^{*-}} - Eox_{Triplet}^*)$$

$$\Delta G = -e(-0.96V - (-0.48V))$$

$$\Delta G = 0.48 eV$$

The positive Gibbs free energy change suggests that the electron transfer from the triplet state of the dimer to the ground state of **TCAQ** to yield **TCAQ^{•-}** is not feasible.

9.2 Reductive quenching:

The oxidation potential of **DIPEA/DIPEA^{•-}** in THF is 0.93 V vs SCE.¹⁴ Converting it with respect to Fc⁺/Fc, we get the oxidation potential to be 0.53 V.

The reduction potential of the ¹TT state of the dimer can be calculated as below.

$$Ered_{TT}^* = Ered_{dimer} + E_{0,0}/e$$

$$Ered_{TT}^* = -1.64 V + 2.25 V = 0.61 V$$

The reduction potential of the triplet state of the dimer can be calculated as below.

$$Ered_{Triplet}^* = Ered_{dimer} + E_{0,0}/e$$

$$Ered_{TT}^* = -1.64 V + 1.25 V = -0.39 V$$

The driving force for electron transfer from **DIPEA** to the TT state of the dimer can be calculated as per the following:

$$\Delta G = -e(Ered_{TT}^* - Eox_{DIPEA/DIPEA^{*-}})$$

$$\Delta G = -e(0.61V - 0.53 V)$$

$$\Delta G = -0.08 eV$$

The negative Gibbs free energy change suggests that the electron transfer from **DIPEA** to the TT state of the dimer is feasible.

The driving force for electron transfer from **DIPEA** to the triplet state of the dimer can be calculated as per the following:

$$\Delta G = -e(Ered_{Triplet}^* - Eox_{DIPEA/DIPEA^{*-}})$$

$$\Delta G = -e(-0.39V - 0.53 V)$$

$$\Delta G = 0.92 eV$$

The positive Gibbs free energy change suggests that the electron transfer from **DIPEA** to the triplet state of the dimer is feasible.

Similarly, the driving force of the other electron donors and acceptors can be calculated. They are summarized below in Table S8. (For **TTF**, the potentials in DCM are taken from Martín.¹⁵ For Chloranil, in DCM, the potential is taken from Nakamura *et al.*¹ For **4F-TCNQ** in DCM, the potentials are taken from Kivala *et al.*¹⁶

Table S8: Table having values of reduction potentials, oxidation potentials (vs Fc⁺/Fc) of the dimer and involved quenchers, and driving force for electron transfer.

$E_{ox} = 0.77\text{ V}$ $E_{red} = -1.64\text{ V}$ (Tcdimer)	E_{ox}	E_{red}	$E_{red}^*(\text{triplet})$ Or $E_{ox}^*(\text{triplet})$	$E_{red}^*(\text{TT})$ Or $E_{ox}^*(\text{TT})$	$\Delta G(\text{triplet, substrate})$	$\Delta G(\text{TT, substrate})$
DIPEA	0.53V	-	-0.39V	0.61V	0.92 eV	-0.08eV
TTF	-0.03V, 0.27V	-	-0.39V	0.61 V	0.36eV,0.66eV	-0.64eV,-0.34eV
Chloranil	-	-0.36V	-0.48 V	-1.48 V	-0.12eV	-1.12eV
TCAQ	-	-0.96 V,-1.84V	-0.48 V	-1.48 V	0.48eV,1.36eV	-0.52eV,0.36eV
4F-TCNQ	-	0.19 V,-0.48 V	-0.48 V	-1.48 V	-0.67eV,0.0 eV	-1.67eV,-0.98 eV

10. Additional quenching experiments

Figure S40: (a) Time profiles at 525 nm when **Tcdimer** is excited at 545 nm in THF upon adding increasing concentrations of **TCAQ**, showing no quenching of the triplet lifetime. (b) Time profiles at 525 nm of **Tcdimer** upon adding increasing concentrations of **DIPEA**, showing quenching of the TT state. (c) Time profiles at 525 nm of **Tcdimer** upon adding 8mM TTF. The black dotted lines represent the fits and the colored dashed lines represent the expected intensity if we assume the TT state acts as the singlet without any recombination.

The amount of quenching of the TT state is estimated from the reduction in the first time component in the decay at 525 nm, which monitors the TT and T₁ excited state absorption. Without quencher the TT decay from 100% signal to 50 % occurs with a time constant of 107 ns in THF. With 4 mM TCAQ this decay is reduced to 66 ns, yielding a quenching efficiency of: $1 - \tau_{TCAQ}/\tau_0 = 1 - 66/107 = 0.38 = 38\%$ (Table S9 and Figure 3a in main manuscript).

The remaining triplet signal if all quenched TT states are unable to form triplets would then originate from the 62% remaining TT population. As the T₁ signal is half as intense as the TT signal as we have concluded that 1 TT state results in only 1 T₁, the 62% TT remaining after quenching would yield a triplet population resulting in 31% of the original signal at 525 nm.

Table S9. Fitting parameters to TT decay profiles measured at 525 nm. * At these higher concentrations, the quenching efficiency calculated would be dynamic quenching efficiency as contributions from static quenching can exist.

Samples in THF	TT Lifetimes	Quenching efficiency	Expected triplet intensity	Observed triplet intensity
Tcdimer	107 ns	-	-	50%
Tcdimer with 4 mM TCAQ	66 ns	38 %	31%	36%
Tcdimer with 16 mM TCAQ*	23 ns	80%	10%	25%
Tcdimer with 8 mM DIPEA	88 ns	17%	41.5%	46%
Tcdimer with 33 mM DIPEA	53 ns	50%	25%	36%
Tcdimer with 8 mM TTF*	23 ns	80%	10%	25%

Figure S41: Flowchart showing the calculation for the expected signal intensity given in Table S9. Initially, if we start with 100% of signal at the TT state, without any quencher, we get 50% of signal after 100 ns corresponding to one free triplet. In the presence of quencher, 4mM TCAQ, the lifetime gets quenched to 66 ns, based on which we get 38% as the quenching efficiency. We can then calculate the expected triplet intensity based on the unquenched TT population (100 -38) % which gives 31% as the Tc-Tc⁺ does not contribute to the signal.

Figure S42: (a) nsTA spectra of *Tcdimer* in THF when excited at 545 nm (b) nsTA spectra of *Tcdimer* in THF with 4mM TCAQ when excited at 545 nm (c) nsTA spectra of *Tcdimer* in THF with 16 mM TCAQ when excited at 545 nm (d) nsTA spectra of *Tcdimer* in THF with 8 mM TTF when excited at 545 nm

As reference, the quenching of TIPS-Tc and Tcmonomer S_1 by TCAQ and TTF was also investigated, shown in Figure S42-S45. The fluorescence quenching in TCSPC experiments was used to verify quenching of the S_1 state. The relative triplet yield was determined from the amplitude of the long-lived triplet signal in nsTA measurements.

Figure S43: (a) Fluorescence decays of *TIPS-Tc* at 550 nm upon addition of 16 mM *TCAQ* in THF. (b) Time profiles of delta absorbance at 502 nm of *TIPS-Tc* upon addition of 16 mM *TCAQ* in THF. (c) Fluorescence decays of *TIPS-Tc* at 550 nm upon addition of 8 mM *TTF* in toluene. (d) Time profiles of delta absorbance at 502 of *TIPS-Tc* upon addition of 8 mM *TTF* in toluene.

Figure S44: TCSPC decay at 546 nm of *Tcmonomer* (when excited at 470 nm) on adding 16 mM *TCAQ* in THF. The lifetime (monoexponential fit) gets quenched from 4.2 ns to 2.4 ns upon adding 16 mM *TCAQ*.

Figure S45: The time trace of **Tcmonomer** at 516 nm upon adding increasing concentrations of **TCAQ** in THF showing negligible quenching of the triplet state.

Figure S46: Spectra of **Tcmonomer** at different time intervals comparing the spectra with (blue) and without (black) 16 mM **TCAQ**. The samples were excited at 542 nm in THF.

Figure S47: The time trace of **Tcdimer** at 600 nm upon adding increasing concentrations of **Chl** in THF, showing no quenching of the triplet.

Figure S48: The time trace of **Tcdimer** at 525 nm upon adding 720 μM concentration of **Chl** in PhCN, showing no quenching of the TT state.

11. Determination of the electron transfer yield:

11.1 ET yield from Tcdimer to Chl

To determine the electron transfer yield from **Tcdimer** to chloranil (**Chl**), the following equation was used:

$$\phi_{ET} = \frac{\Delta Abs_{Chl-}}{\Delta Abs_{ZnTPP}} \times \frac{\epsilon_{T,ZnTPP}}{\epsilon_{Chl-}} \times \frac{1-10^{(-Abs_{525nm,ZnTPP})}}{1-10^{(-Abs_{525nm,dimer})}} \times \phi_{T,ZnTPP} \dots \dots \dots (S5)$$

The experiment was done at low powers (~ 160 μJ/pulse) to avoid triplet triplet annihilation in ZnTPP. The molar extinction coefficient of reduced chloranil anion at 450 nm is 9700 M⁻¹cm¹.¹⁷ The yield was calculated at a time delay of 10 μs using values listed in Tables S10 and S11.

Figure S49: (a) Spectra of **Tcdimer** with 630 μM and 720 μM concentrations of **Chl** in PhCN upon exciting at 552 nm at 10 μs (b) Spectra of ZnTPP in toluene upon exciting at 552 nm at 10 μs .

Table S10: Table summarizing the values used for determining the ET yield with **Tcdimer** at 630 μM **Chl**.

	ΔAbs at 10 μs .	Abs at 552 nm	$\varepsilon(\text{M}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1})$	ϕ_T	$\Delta(\Delta\text{Abs})$	$\Delta\varepsilon(\text{M}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1})$
ZnTPP	0.0087 (470 nm)	0.052	78000	0.90	0.0003	8000
Chl anion	0.0022 (450 nm)	0.5 (Tcdimer)	9700	0.29	0.0004	990

Table S11: Table summarizing the values used for determining the ET yield with **Tcdimer** at 720 μM **Chl**.

	ΔAbs at 10 μs .	Abs at 552 nm	$\varepsilon(\text{M}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1})$	ϕ_T	$\Delta(\Delta\text{Abs})$	$\Delta\varepsilon(\text{M}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1})$
ZnTPP	0.0087 (470 nm)	0.052	78000	0.90	0.0003	8000
Chl anion	0.0026 (450 nm)	0.5 (Tcdimer)	9700	0.35	0.0004	990

The error in the ET yield was calculated using the following equation using values listed in the above table:

$$\frac{\Delta\phi_{ET}}{\phi_{ET}} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\Delta(\Delta\text{Abs}_{\text{Chl}^-})}{\Delta\text{Abs}_{\text{Chl}^-}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\Delta(\Delta\text{Abs}_{\text{ZnTPP}})}{\Delta\text{Abs}_{\text{ZnTPP}}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\Delta(\varepsilon_{\text{Chl}^-})}{\varepsilon_{\text{Chl}^-}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\Delta(\varepsilon_{\text{T,ZnTPP}})}{\varepsilon_{\text{T,ZnTPP}}}\right)^2}$$

Hence, the ET yield obtained at 630 μM and 720 μM concentrations of **Chl** are $29 \pm 6.8\%$ and $35 \pm 7.1\%$ respectively.

11.2 ET yield from Tc-BP-Tc to 4F-TCNQ

In a similar manner, the ET yield from **Tc-BP-Tc** triplet to **4F-TCNQ** at 2 μs was calculated using equation S5 and values listed in Table S12 and Table S13:

Figure S50: (a) Spectra of **Tc-BP-Tc** with 385 μM concentration of **4F-TCNQ** in PhCN upon exciting at 548 nm at 2 μs (b) Spectra of ZnTPP in toluene upon exciting at 548 nm at 2 μs .

Table S12: Table summarizing the values used for determining the ET yield with **Tc-BP-Tc** at 385 μM **4F-TCNQ**.

	ΔAbs at 2 μs .	Abs at 548 nm	$\epsilon(\text{M}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1})$	ϕ_T	$\Delta(\Delta\text{Abs})$	$\Delta\epsilon(\text{M}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1})$
ZnTPP	0.01 (470 nm)	0.096	78000	0.90	0.0003	8000
4F-TCNQ anion	0.0044 (757 nm)	0.55 (Tc-BP-Tc)	19000	0.45	0.0008	1938

Figure S51: (a) Spectra of **Tc-BP-Tc** with 393 μM concentration of **4F-TCNQ** in PhCN upon exciting at 548 nm at 2 μs (b) Spectra of ZnTPP in toluene upon exciting at 548 nm at 2 μs .

Table S13: Table summarizing the values used for determining the ET yield with **Tc-BP-Tc** at 393 μM **4F-TCNQ**.

	ΔAbs at 2 μs .	Abs at 548 nm	$\epsilon(\text{M}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1})$	ϕ_T	$\Delta(\Delta\text{Abs})$	$\Delta\epsilon(\text{M}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1})$
ZnTPP	0.016 (470 nm)	0.13	78000	0.90	0.0003	8000
4F-TCNQ anion	0.0061 (757 nm)	0.67 (Tc-BP-Tc)	19000	0.47	0.0008	1938

The reported literature value of the molar extinction coefficient of the reduced **4F-TCNQ** anion at 757 nm was used.¹⁸ The error is also calculated as in section 11.1, and we obtain electron transfer yields from **Tc-BP-Tc** to **4F-TCNQ** of $45 \pm 10\%$ and $47 \pm 8\%$ for **4F-TCNQ** concentrations of 385 μM and 393 μM , respectively.

Table S14. Fitting parameters to TT decay profiles measured at 520 nm for **Tc-BP-Tc**.^{*} At these higher concentrations the quenching efficiency calculated would be dynamic quenching efficiency as contributions from static quenching can exist.

Samples in THF	TT Lifetimes	Quenching efficiency	Expected triplet intensity	Observed triplet intensity
Tc-BP-Tc	372 ns	-	-	36%
Tc-BP-Tc with 4 mM TCAQ	154 ns	58 %	15%	18%
Tc-BP-Tc with 16 mM TCAQ [*]	41 ns	89%	4%	8%

Figure S52: Flowchart showing the calculation for the expected signal intensity given in Table S14. Initially, if we start with 100% of signal at the TT state, without any quencher, we get 36% of signal after 100 ns corresponding to one free triplet. In the presence of quencher, 4mM TCAQ, the lifetime gets quenched to 153 ns, based on which we get 58% as the quenching efficiency. We can then calculate the expected triplet intensity based on the unquenched TT population (100 - 58) % which gives 15% as the Tc-Tc⁺ does not contribute to the signal.

11.3 Collision rate calculations:

The collision rate was calculated as per the following equation:

$$k_T = k_T^0 + k_c[Q]$$

Where k_T represents decay of the triplet in the presence of the quencher, k_T^0 represents the decay of the unquenched triplet, k_c represents the collision rate and $[Q]$ is the concentration of the quencher.

Figure S53: Triplet decay rates of (a) Tcdimer with Chloranil upto 100 μM , with the slope yielding a value of $2 \times 10^8 \text{ M}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ as the collision rate. Beyond 100 μM , the decays were biexponential due to which a linear fit was not suitable. (b) Tc-BP-Tc with 4F-TCNQ with the slope yielding a value of $6 \times 10^9 \text{ M}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ as the collision rate.

12. Low Temperature nsTA experiments:

Figure S54: (a) The time profiles of the signal at 519 nm of Tc-BP-Tc in MeTHF when excited at 543 nm. The initial decay (TT state) increases from 400 ns to 3.5 μs from 285 K to 100 K. (b) The time profiles of the signal at 525 nm of Tcdimer in MeTHF when excited at 545 nm. The initial decay (TT state) increases from 110 ns to 350 ns from 280 K to 100 K.

13 Additional tr-EPR data:

Figure S55: Time-dependent evolution of the tr-EPR spectra of **Tcmonomer** recorded at 80 K.

Figure S56: Time-dependent evolution of the tr-EPR spectra of *Tcdimer* recorded at 80 K.

Figure S57: Time-dependent evolution of the tr-EPR spectra of **Tc-BP-Tc** recorded at 80 K.

Pulsed EPR data:

Field-dependent transient nutation experiments were performed at the Q-band for Tcdimer and are presented in Figure S58. Assuming S and M_S are good quantum numbers and the mw radiation excites a single transition, the observed nutation frequencies follow

$$\omega_{nut}(m_S, m_{S+1}) = \omega_1 \sqrt{S(S+1) - m_S(m_S+1)}$$

where $\omega_1 = g_1 \mu_B B_1 / \hbar$

the

$\overline{B_1}$ field strength can be determined from a reference measurement and the g-factors are known, the S and M_S quantum numbers can be determined from the nutation frequency. The field-positions chosen for the transient nutation experiments are indicated in Figure S56(a) alongside the two-pulse echo-detected field sweep and the time- and frequency-domain transient nutation data are presented in Figure S56(b,c). The transient nutation data indicate two clear nutation frequencies in agreement with the $\sqrt{2\omega_1}$ and $\sqrt{6\omega_1}$ frequencies, characteristic of the $|1, \pm 1\rangle \leftrightarrow |1, 0\rangle$ and $|2, \pm 1\rangle \leftrightarrow |2, 0\rangle$ transitions, providing evidence

for the existence of strongly coupled triplet pairs and free triplets at different field positions, consistent with the discussion and assignment of the trEPR spectrum in the main text.

Figure S58: (a) Echo-detected fieldsweep for Tcdimer recorded at the Q-band, 80 K with a 700 ns delay following the 548 nm LASER pulse. The field positions used in transient nutation experiments are indicated by the coloured vertical lines. Transient nutation data as a function of the length of the first microwave pulse t_p (b) and the corresponding Fourier transforms (c) for Tcdimer recorded in frozen toluene solution at 80 K. The frequency abscissa is normalised against a reference nutation frequency measured for a spin-1/2. Frequencies relevant for triplet and quintet states are indicated with the grey vertical lines.

Scheme 1: Scheme showing possible pathways occurring in Tcdimer upon photoexcitation

14. Computational details

14.1 Absorption of Tcdimer, TIPS-Tc and linker

Figure S59: Experimental UV-Visible spectra of the linker, TIPS-Tc and Tcdimer in THF.

Absorption features of **Tcdimer**, in particular that observed experimentally in the 380-420 nm region, were explored computationally considering individual relevant fragments. All geometries were optimized at the CAM-B3LYP/6-31G(d) level of theory and vertical excitations were obtained using TDADFT at the same level.

Figure S60. Simulated UV-Vis spectra of the linker (black line), TIPS-Tc (orange), TIPS-Tc-linker (yellow), Tcdimer-syn (light green), Tcdimer-anti (green) and Tcdimer-anti without the linker (dashed dark green).

The low energy band corresponds to excitations on the tetracene unit of TIPS-Tc and TIPS-Tc-linker, and to the bright state resulting from the coupling between the excitations localized on the Tc units of the Tcdimer with and without linker (Figure S61). The absorption spectrum of the Tcdimer without the linker closely matches that of TIPS-Tc, with a distribution of states corresponding to that of the excitonic states arising from its S_1 - S_3 states (Table S15).

Addition of the linker to TIPS-Tc leads to the emergence of additional states with mixed local and charge transfer (CT) character. In particular, S_2 and S_3 are dominantly CT. The band computed at about 360 nm for the Tcdimer arises from the coupling of these excitations involving the Tc units and the linker; accordingly, they do not appear when considering the Tcdimer without linker.

Table S15: Excitation energy (in eV) and associated oscillator strength for the low-lying singlet states of the fragments computed at their respective ground state geometries at the CAM-B3LYP/6-31G(d) level.

	TIPS-Tc	TIPS-Tc-linker	Tcdimer anti	Tcdimer anti no linker
S_1	2.795 (0.523)	2.746 (0.445)	2.734 (0.870)	2.793 (0.000)
S_2	3.726 (0.025)	3.525 (0.190)	2.747 (0.000)	2.797 (1.033)
S_3	3.966 (0.112)	3.797 (1.411)	3.419 (3.001)	3.720 (0.052)
S_4		3.984 (0.779)	3.493 (0.000)	3.720 (0.000)
S_5			3.584 (1.087)	3.964 (0.016)
S_6			3.853 (0.000)	3.964 (0.207)
S_7			3.922 (0.000)	
S_8			3.929 (0.210)	

Figure S61. Electron/hole pair densities (orange/blue) for the S_1 , S_3 and S_5 states of Tcdimer-anti as obtained at its ground state geometry at the CAM-B3LYP/6-31G(d) level in gas phase.

Figure S62. Electron/hole pair densities (orange/blue) for the S_1 - S_4 states of TIPC-Tc-linker as obtained at its ground state geometry at the CAM-B3LYP/6-31G(d) level in gas phase.

14.2 Tcdimer anti/syn conformers

Figure S63. (left) Rigid scan around the acetylene bond and (right) geometry of the anti and syn conformers of the **Tcdimer** with associated value of the dihedral angle and relative Gibbs free energy.

The *syn* conformer is found to be only slightly less stable than the *anti* counterpart, and accessible via a low rotational barrier (Figure S63).

14.3 Photophysical properties of anticonformers of Tcdimer with chloranil and TCAQ

Ground and quintet states geometries of **Tcdimer-Chl**, **Tc-dimer-TCAQ** and **Tc-BP-Tc** without and with chloranil, were optimized using density functional theory (DFT) at the CAM-B3LYP/6-31G(d) level. Several starting geometries were considered to explore the conformational space of the dimers. CT state geometries were optimized within the framework of time-dependent DFT at the same level of theory. On the basis of the lowest energy structure obtained for each dimer, vertical excitations were computed at the same level of theory within the framework of time-dependent DFT with the Tamm-Dancoff approximation (TDADFT). All calculations were done with the Gaussian 16 program package.¹⁹ The DrawMol program was used for visualisation of the molecular orbitals.²⁰

Figure S64: Geometry of the lowest energy dimer of (a) **Tcdimer-Chl** and (b) **Tcdimer-TCAQ**.

Table S16: Excitation energy (in eV) and contributions (>5%) for the low-lying triplet states of **Tcdimer-Chl** computed at the ground state and triplet-pair (quintet) optimized geometries.

state	ΔE	contrib. %	
GS geometry			
³ LE2 (Tc2)	1.299	H→L+2	72
		H→L+1	8
		H-1→L+2	8
³ LE1 (Tc1)	1.328	H-1→L+1	72
		H→L+1	6
		H-1→L+2	5
³ CT	1.442	H-1→L	84
		H→L	9
TT (LE1+LE2)	2.627		
quintet geometry			
³ LE2 (Tc2)	0.693	H→L+2	83
		H→L+1	5
³ LE1 (Tc1)	0.736	H-1→L+1	82
³ CT	1.168	H-1→L	92
		H→L	5
TT (LE1+LE2)	1.429		
CT geometry			

³ CT	0.594	H-1→L	16
		H→L	81
³ LE1 (Tc1)	1.062	H-1→L+1	15
		H→L+1	71
³ LE2 (Tc2)	1.300	H-1→L+2	69
		H→L+2	15

Table S17: Excitation energy (in eV) and contributions for the low-lying triplet states of **Tcdimer-TCAQ** computed at the ground state and triplet-pair (quintet) optimized geometries.

state	ΔE	contrib. %	
GS geometry			
³ LE1 (Tc1)	1.288	H-1→L+1	80
³ LE2 (Tc2)	1.299	H→L+2	82
³ CT	2.341	H-1→L	49
		H-2→L+1	6
TT (LE1+LE2)	2.587		
quintet geometry			
³ LE1 (Tc1)	0.666	H-1→L	23
		H-1→L+1	67
³ LE2 (Tc2)	0.693	H→L+2	90
³ CT	2.099	H-1→L	69
		H-1→L+1	24
TT (LE1+LE2)	1.359		
CT geometry*			
³ LE1' (Tc1)	1.013	H-1→L	10
		H-1→L+1	31
		H→L	13
		H→L+1	37
³ CT	1.107	H-1→L	32
		H-1→L+1	9
		H→L	42
		H→L+1	11
³ LE2' (Tc2)	1.299	H-1→L+2	46
		H→L+2	39

*here, the two LE states nomenclature is maintained for ease of comparison throughout the different geometries considered, a prime mark is used to denote their more mixed nature

Figure S65: Molecular orbitals of (left) *Tcdimer-Chl* and (right) *Tcdimer-TCAQ* at their respective ground state geometry.

Figure S66: Molecular orbitals of (left) *Tcdimer-Chl* and (right) *Tcdimer-TCAQ* at their respective CT state geometry.

14.4 Photophysical properties of *syn* conformers with chloranil

To address the possible effect of conformational heterogeneity, we explored the *syn01-Chl* and *syn02-Chl* Tcdimers, where the chloranil molecule sits on one or the other of the Tc units. The two optimized dimers and the *anti-Chl* (**Tcdimer-Chl**) one show relative Gibbs free energies within 1 kcal/mol, in the following order: *syn02-Chl* < *anti-Chl* < *syn01-Chl*. On the basis of the two *syn* structures obtained, we computed vertical excitations at the CAM-B3LYP/6-31G(d) level of theory within the framework of time-dependent DFT with the Tamm-Dancoff approximation (TDADFT).

Table S18: Excitation energy (in eV) and contributions (>5%) for the low-lying triplet states of **syn01-Chl** computed at the ground state and triplet-pair (quintet) optimized geometries.

state	ΔE	contrib. %	
GS geometry			
³ LE2(Tc2)	1.297	H→L+2	72
(Tc1→Tc2)		H-1→L+2	9
(Tc2→Tc1)		H→L+1	8
³ LE1(Tc1)	1.327	H-1→L+1	71
(Tc2→Tc1)		H→L+1	6
(Tc1→Tc2)		H-1→L+2	5
³ CT (Tc1→Chl)	1.433	H-1→L	83
(Tc2→Chl)		H→L	9
TT (LE1+LE2)	2.624		
quintet geometry			
³ LE2 (Tc2)	0.689	H→L+2	86
³ LE1 (Tc1)	0.738	H-1→L+1	85
³ CT (Tc1→Chl)	1.161	H-1→L	93
TT (LE1+LE2)	1.427		

Table S19: Excitation energy (in eV) and contributions (>5%) for the low-lying triplet states of **syn02-Chl** computed at the ground state and triplet-pair (quintet) optimized geometries.

state	ΔE	contrib. %	
GS geometry			
³ LE1(Tc1)	1.298	H→L+2	73
(Tc2→Tc1)		H-1→L+2	9
(Tc1→Tc2)		H→L+1	7
³ LE2(Tc2)	1.325	H-1→L+1	75
(Tc1→Tc2)		H→L+1	6
³ CT (Tc2→Chl)	1.416	H-1→L	87
(Tc1→Chl)		H→L	9
TT (LE1+LE2)	2.623		
quintet geometry			
³ LE1 (Tc1)	0.693	H→L+2	84
³ LE2 (Tc2)	0.737	H-1→L+1	85
³ CT (Tc2→Chl)	1.145	H-1→L	93
TT (LE1+LE2)	1.430		

Figure S67. Molecular orbitals of (left) *syn01-Chl* and (right) *syn02-Chl* at their respective ground state geometry.

14.5 Photophysical properties of *Tc-BP-Tc* and *Tc-BP-Tc-Chl*

Figure S68: Geometry of the stable trans and cis conformers of the **Tc-BP-Tc**.

Table S20: Structural parameters of the cis dimers: α angle between the Tc units long axis, θ_1 biphenyl dihedral angle

	α	θ_1
cis01	24	62
cis02	61	60
cis03	129	59

We considered both trans and cis type geometries as starting point for exploring the conformational space of **Tc-BP-Tc**. All cis dimers are found to be more stable than the trans counterpart, with notably two conformers being almost isoenergetic. These structures differ in the relative orientation of the tetracene moieties which translate into varying extent of stacking of the Tc units. In the following, we focus on the two most stable conformers, cis01 and cis02.

Table S21: Excitation energy (in eV) and contributions (>5%) for the low-lying triplet states of **cis01-Chl** computed at the ground state and triplet-pair (quintet) optimized geometries.

state	ΔE	contrib. %		
GS geometry				
T ₁	(Tc1→Chl)	1.304	H-1→L	15
	LE(Tc1)		H-1→L+1	26
	(Tc1→Tc2)		H-1→L+2	10
	(Tc2→Tc1)		H→L+1	14
	LE(Tc2)		H→L+2	23
T ₂	(Tc1→Chl)	1.307	H-1→L	10
	LE(Tc1)		H-1→L+1	22
	(Tc1→Tc2)		H-1→L+2	5
	LE(Tc2)		H→L+2	52
T ₃	(Tc1→Chl)	1.392	H-1→L	51
	LE(Tc1)		H-1→L+1	24
	(Tc2→Chl)		H→L	15

	(Tc2→Tc1)		H→L+1	6
T4	(Tc1→Chl)	2.307	H-1→L	21
	(Tc2→Chl)		H→L	77
TT (LE1+LE2)	2.611			
quintet geometry				
³ LE2 (Tc2)	0.690		H→L+2	77
			H-1→L+2	12
			H→L+1	5
³ LE1 (Tc1)	0.727		H-1→L+1	69
			H→L+1	13
			H-1→L	7
³ CT1 (Tc1→Chl)	1.094		H-1→L	74
			H→L	17
			H-1→L+1	6
³ CT2 (Tc2→Chl)	1.997		H→L	79
			H-1→L	18
TT (LE1+LE2)	1.417			
CT geometry				
³ CT1 (Tc1→Chl)	0.497		H→L	82
			H-1→L	17
³ LE1 (Tc1)	1.061		H→L+1	73
			H-1→L+1	18
³ LE2 (Tc2)	1.304		H-1→L+2	67
			H→L+2	22
³ CT2 (Tc2→Chl)	1.593		H-1→L	80
			H→L	17

Table S22: Excitation energy (in eV) and contributions (>5%) for the low-lying triplet states of **cis02-Chl** computed at the ground state and triplet-pair (quintet) optimized geometries.

state	ΔE	contrib. %	
GS geometry			
³ LE2 (Tc2)	1.285	H→L+2	82
		H→L+1	7
³ LE1 (Tc1)	1.337	H-1→L+1	78
		H-1→L+2	6
		H-1→L	5
³ CT1 (Tc1→Chl)	1.413	H-1→L	91
		H-1→L+1	5
³ CT2 (Tc2→Chl)	2.320	H→L	96
TT (LE1+LE2)	2.622		
quintet geometry			
³ LE2 (Tc2)	0.645	H→L+2	84
		H→L+1	9
³ LE1 (Tc1)	0.736	H-1→L+1	84
		H-1→L+2	8
³ CT1 (Tc1→Chl)	1.143	H-1→L	97
³ CT2 (Tc2→Chl)	2.037	H→L	98
TT (LE1+LE2)	1.381		
CT geometry			
³ CT1 (Tc1→Chl)	0.587	H→L	98
³ LE1 (Tc1)	1.071	H→L+1	90
³ LE2 (Tc2)	1.288	H-1→L+2	89
³ CT2 (Tc2→Chl)	1.676	H-1→L	99

Figure S69. Molecular orbitals of (left) *cis01*-Chl and (right) *cis02*-Chl at their respective ground state geometry.

Figure S70. Molecular orbitals of (left) *cis01-Chl* and (right) *cis02-Chl* at their respective CT state geometry.

14.6 Modelling the second electron transfer in Tcdimer-Chl and Tc-BP-Tc-Chl

The second electron transfer is expected to be virtually unaffected by the first CT at the other tetracene unit. To address this, the **Tcdimer-Chl** system in its cation state is considered as the starting point for the second electron transfer, where one tetracene unit is already oxidized (${}^3\text{Tc-Tc}^+$). At this optimized geometry, where the positive charge is localized over the non-interacting tetracene unit, the CT state energy for **Tcdimer-Chl** cation without and with a negative point charge placed next to the oxidized tetracene amounts to 1.59 eV and 1.53 eV, respectively, values comparable to that of the first electron transfer (1.44 eV, see Table S16). At the optimized geometry of **cis01-Chl** and **cis02-Chl** in their cation state, the CT state energy (without placing a negative point charge next to the oxidized tetracene unit) amounts to 1.65 eV and 1.67 eV, respectively.

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